

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D8.1 Summary of Bi-monthly reports

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Executive Summary

The COVINFORM project is implementing a multidisciplinary and intersectional approach to examine how vulnerability is defined and addressed in COVID-19 responses from government, public health, and communication perspectives. The project also aims to examine the impact that different national, regional, and local responses have had on vulnerable and marginalized groups and view these impacts through an intersectional perspective to understand how different factors interconnect, potentially further increasing vulnerability and marginalization.

In line with the objectives of the project, this report aims to provide an overview of the activities implemented within WP8 “Development of solutions, guidelines and recommendations” and in particular within task 8.1 devoted to “Develop and publish bi-monthly reports for different target groups” during the first 18 months of the project. The deliverable is organised as follows: in the first section a synthesis of the objectives and of the content of the first 8 bi-monthly reports published within task 8.1 is provided. In the second section the content of the published bi-monthly report is presented. Finally in the conclusions section future steps and objectives of the task are drafted.

It is worth emphasising that this report will be updated in M36 with a summary of the content of bi-monthly reports that will be published between month 19 and month 36 of the COVINFORM project.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable aims to present the work conducted within Task 8.1, under WP8, in the first 18 months of the COVINFORM project. WP8, coordinated by the Sapienza University of Rome (SAPIENZA) team, aims to create reports and materials for stakeholders and to develop recommendations and best practices to influence adherence to behavioural advice across different groups in society. In particular, the objective of task 8.1, coordinated by the same team, is to create and publish useful output of the project every two months in the form of brief reports, snippets, webinars, etc. for the different stakeholders. The task started in month 3 of the project, with the first report published in January 2021, and will end with the end of the project, with the last report to be published in September 2023.

A total of 8 bi-monthly reports were published until now, 7 in brochure format and 1 in video format. In deciding the different topics of the reports, we tried to follow both the development of the pandemic, focusing on topics connected to the crisis, and the evolution of the project, focusing on the findings coming from the activities and analysis conducted in the various WPs. An overview of the reports is presented in Table 1. The full reports are available in the section 2 of the deliverable and on the project website. The authors of the different reports vary depending on the topics covered (Table 1). The reports containing the results of the project's activities were written, under the supervision of the SAPIENZA team, directly by the COVINFORM partners leading the activities. All the reports have been published on the project website¹ and disseminated via the social media channels of the project. Lastly, the reports in video format have been published on the YouTube channel of the project.

The first two reports published in the very first months of the project were dedicated to the analysis of a topic that, at that time, was strongly connected with the evolution of the pandemic and the measures adopted to counter it, namely the topic of vaccines and vaccination campaigns. The first report, published in January 2021, and titled "COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts", opens with a brief review of the history of vaccines, and then describes the current (as of January 2021) situation regarding COVID-19 vaccines, also exploring the issue of misinformation related to these types of vaccines. The second report, published in March 2021 and entitled "COVID-19 vaccination campaign in COVINFORM countries: infographics & best practices", contains an overview of the progress of vaccination campaigns in the COVINFORM partners countries and a focus on the best practices adopted in the vaccination campaign conducted in Israel. On this topic, Elena Ambrosetti and Marina Zannella from SAPIENZA team conducted an interview (available on the YouTube channel of the project and accessible by a multimedia link in the same report) with Chaim Rafalowski from the Magen David Adom (MDA) in Israel. As the two reports were published at the early stage of the project, it was impossible to target any specific stakeholder, therefore the report was aimed to provide an informed overview of vaccination campaign for the whole population.

¹ Available at: <https://www.covinform.eu/project-outputs/bi-monthly-reports/>

Table 1. Overview of the bi-monthly reports published from the 3rd month to the 18th month of the project

Number	Date of publication	Title	Topics covered	Authors and contributors	Format
1	January 2021	COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts	History of vaccines, progress of COVID-19 vaccines, misinformation	E. Ambrosetti & M. Zannella (SAPIENZA) D. Bertel (SYNYO) S. Anson (TRI) A. Hernández Tejedor (SAMUR) M. Parzonka & C. Pannofino (TRI) <i>as contributors</i>	Brochure
2	March 2021	COVID-19 vaccination campaign in COVINFORM countries: infographics & best practices	Vaccinations in COVINFORM partners countries and vaccination campaign in Israel	E. Ambrosetti & M Zannella (SAPIENZA) I. Laist & C. Rafalowski (MDA)	Brochure and video-interview
3	May 2021	A Glimpse of the Lessons Learned During the COVID-19 Pandemic	Findings and best practices about communication from desk-based research within T7.1	D. Antunes & J. M. Palma-Oliveira (FS)	Brochure
4	July 2021	Findings on the Governmental Responses in COVINFORM countries	Findings about governmental responses from desk-based research within T4.1	T. Spathi, I. Bagkatzounis, M. Arabatzi, A. Tsekoura, D. Papadaki & I. Eliezer (KEMEA)	Brochure
5	September 2021	Using an intersectional lens to understand the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic	Findings about public health impact and responses from desk-based research within T5.1, intersectionality theory	J. Molenaar (UANTWERPEN)	Brochure
6	November 2021	The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare workers	Impact of the pandemic on health and psychosocial conditions of HCW	G. Anderson (UCSC) E. Polimadei (SAPIENZA)	Brochure
7	January 2022	Viruses of the mind. Coping and joking about COVID-19	Findings about an analysis on the role of humour during the pandemic	D. Bertel & V. Adler (SYNYO)	Brochure
8	March 2022	After two years of pandemic: COVINFORM partners talk about the experiences, challenges and lessons learned	Two video stories from two practitioners about the experiences in their work during the pandemic	M. Stickler (AUTRC) P. Miravet (SAMUR)	Video-interviews

The reports three to five contain findings from the desk-based research conducted within WP4, WP5, and WP7. Specifically, in the report “A Glimpse of the Lessons Learned During the COVID-19 Pandemic”, published in May 2021, are summarized the findings and best practices on communication practices during the pandemic in the COVINFORM partner countries, emerged from the desk-based research activity conducted within the task 7.1, coordinated by the Factor Social (FS) team. The fourth report, published in July 2021, entitled “Findings on the Governmental Responses in COVINFORM countries”, summarizes the principal findings on the desk-based research regarding the institutional and government responses, conducted within the task 4.1 under the supervision of The Center for Security Studies (KEMEA) team. The fifth report, “Using an intersectional lens to understand the unequal impact of the COVID-19 pandemic”, published in September 2021, recaps insights from desk-based research about COVID-19 public health impact and responses in COVINFORM partner countries, done within the task 5.1, under the coordination of the University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN) team. Compared to the first two reports, those three reports and the following one targeted more specifically academic and practitioners.

The sixth report, “The impact of COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare workers”, published in November 2021, is devoted to a topic that is relevant within the studies concerning the consequences of the pandemic and that is going to be one of the case studies implemented within the project (WP3), namely the health and wellbeing of healthcare workers and the impact and the consequences of COVID-19 on this particular population category.

The seventh report, published in January 2022 and titled “Virus of the mind. Coping and joking about COVID-19” summarizes the main findings of an exploratory analysis of memes conducted within task 7.3 and coordinated by Synyo GmbH (SYNYO) team.

The eighth report, published in March 2022 and entitled “After two years of pandemic” is the first report published entirely in video format. It is the first of a series of videos aimed at collecting the witnesses about two years of pandemic of the operators involved in the project. In particular, in this first video, Marina Stickler from the Austrian Red Cross (AUTRC) and Paloma Miravet from the Spanish Samur-Protección Civil (SAMUR) describe the challenges they had to face in the various phases of the COVID-19 pandemic, focusing also on lessons learned and best practices that have been developed in the crisis situation related to the pandemic.

The remaining part of the deliverable contains all the reports published so far. In the last section of the deliverable, a balance of this first part of bi-monthly reports is drawn and the next steps for the remaining bi-monthly reports are outlined.

COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

COVID-19 Vaccines: History and Facts

Bi-Monthly Report: 01
January 2021

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Disclaimer

The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the authors, and in no way represents the view of the European Commission or its services.

This report cannot and does not contain health advice. The information provided by the COVINFORM project is for general information and education purposes only, and is not a substitute for professional health advice.

Accordingly, before taking any action based upon such information, we encourage you to consult with the appropriate medical and healthcare professionals.

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A CONCISE HISTORY OF VACCINES

In the 20th century, nearly 1.7 billion people died from infectious diseases. Here are some of the most dramatic numbers: 400 million deaths from smallpox, 96.7 million deaths from measles, 38.1 million deaths from whooping cough, more than 37 million deaths from tetanus, 12.7 million deaths from hepatitis B, and nearly 22 million deaths from meningitis¹.

Today, thanks to the use of vaccines, cases of diphtheria, measles, rubella, mumps, whooping cough, tetanus and diseases caused by *Haemophilus influenzae*, have been reduced by 98 percent, proving that the vaccines are the most effective medicines in the world. In the Western world, mass vaccinations have prevented the deaths of 500 million people (slightly more than the current total population of the 27 EU countries in 2020)².

The first vaccine, the one against the smallpox, was introduced at the end of the 18th century by the British doctor Edward Jenner. Jenner had the intuition of the vaccine while observing the powers of cowpox to prevent smallpox. Over the last two centuries, the success of vaccines in saving human lives came from predictions made from the study of animal models, natural infections and sero-epidemiology: thanks to those predictions it has been possible to produce protective antibodies. At the end of the 19th century, the French microbiologist Louis Pasteur, adopting a similar technique to the one used by Jenner, introduced the rabies vaccine (1885). From Pasteur onward, the rush toward vaccine production has been impressively fast, at the rate of nearly one vaccine every year (Figure 1)³. In 1886, the vaccines for cholera and typhoid were introduced, in 1897 the vaccine for plague, in 1923 the vaccine for diphtheria, in 1926-1927 the vaccines for whooping cough, tetanus and tuberculosis, in 1935 the vaccine for yellow fever, in 1955 the vaccine for poliomyelitis, between 1963 and 1969 the vaccines for measles, mumps and rubella, and in the following years those against meningitis (various strains in 1975, 1985, 2013), pneumonia (1977), hepatitis B and A (1981, 1995), chickenpox (1995), papilloma virus (2006) and many others for minor diseases.

¹ Information is beautiful. 20th Century Death | [see here](#) & [here](#)

² Grignolio, A. (2016). Chi ha paura dei vaccini? Codice.

³ Plotkin, S. (2014). History of vaccination. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(34), 12283-12287.

The protagonist of post-World War II vaccinology was the American microbiologist Maurice Hilleman (1919-2005), who worked on the measles vaccine. He created nine of the most widely used vaccines today (including those against mumps, rubella, hepatitis A, hepatitis B and pneumonia) and in 1971 developed the second most important combination vaccine after the diphtheria, pertussis (whooping cough), and tetanus vaccine (DPT), namely the trivalent measles-mumps-rubella. Hilleman is perhaps the man who has saved the most lives in history: about eight million a year, according to an estimate published in *Nature*⁴.

Early techniques used for the development of vaccines were based on the production of protective antibodies and on cellular functions able to control pathogen replication in the occurrence of an infection despite the presence of antibodies. These techniques are still crucial even though new strategies for vaccine development already exist⁵.

Figure 1. Timeline of vaccines from 18th to 21st century

⁴ Dove, A. (2005). Maurice Hilleman. *Nature medicine*, 11(4), S2-S2.

⁵ Plotkin, S. A., & Plotkin, S. L. (2011). The development of vaccines: how the past led to the future. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 9(12), 889-893. & Rappuoli, R., Pizza, M., Del Giudice, G., & De Gregorio, E. (2014). Vaccines, new opportunities for a new society. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(34), 12288-12293.

WHAT IS THE CURRENT STATE OF PROGRESS OF COVID VACCINES?

The end of 2020 brought new hope to tackle the pandemic: the approval in several countries of safe and effective vaccines to protect against COVID-19. Since the dawn of the pandemic, scientists around the world have been engaged in a race against time to stop the virus, which to date has claimed 1.926.625 lives globally⁶. Their efforts bore fruits: researchers are testing 289 candidate vaccines today, while 10 are already in use (Figure 2)⁷. Still, there are many challenges to face: countries must organize vaccination strategies and vaccination deployment plans and it will be necessary to keep the guard up for months to come until the immunization of the population is achieved.

Figure 2. Number of existing COVID-19 vaccines by status

⁶ WHO data updated to January 10, 2021. <https://covid19.who.int/>

⁷ COVID-19 vaccine tracker developed by the Vaccine Centre at the London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (data updated to 1 Jan. 2021). https://vac-lshtm.shinyapps.io/ncov_vaccine_landscape/_w_a1ac4096/#

Despite the enthusiasm for these achievements bringing new hope for the future, many people are skeptical regarding the rapidity with which the vaccine was developed. **So how was the rapid development of the vaccine possible?**

COVID-19 vaccines follow the same development procedures as other vaccines but in a compressed time (Figure 3). Different approaches have been used by companies to speed up the development timelines, including combining clinical trial phases and mobilizing more human resources. The compression of time has been facilitated by early and continuous dialogue between developers and regulatory experts, as in the case of the European Medicines Agency (EMA) that offers informal consultation with its COVID-19 Task Force (ETF) and rapid scientific advice ([see here](#)). These different strategies (or their combination) made the fast-track development of COVID-19 vaccines possible without compromising quality and safety standards. Once all the development stages are successfully completed, national and supranational regulators perform quality, safety and efficacy checks for which developers must provide data from all testing / investigations done. Regulators are actively engaged in reducing the timeframe for evaluation as far as safety standards are guaranteed, for example by accessing data as they become available during the development process. After approval, the safety of vaccines is monitored while they are in use to evaluate their efficacy and possible rare side effects.

Figure 3. Vaccines development process

PHARMACEUTICAL QUALITY

Scientists perform small-scale studies to determine the vaccine's final formulation

PRECLINICAL TESTING

Scientists perform in vitro and animal studies to evaluate the immune response generated by the vaccine

↓

CLINICAL TRIALS, PHASE I

The vaccine is given to a small number (generally **20-100**) of **volunteers** to assess its safety and ability to generate an immune response, as well to determine the right dosage

↓

CLINICAL TRIALS, PHASE II

The vaccine is tested on a larger group (**several hundreds**) of **volunteers** to confirm its efficacy and to study the best dosing and the most common side effects

↓

CLINICAL TRIALS, PHASE III

This phase involves **thousands of volunteers** and shows how effective the vaccine is at protecting against the infection and what are the less common side effects

The Vaccine Centre of the London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine [reports](#) that there are currently 220 COVID-19 vaccines in preclinical testing and 70 in clinical evaluation. The detailed status of the progress of vaccine candidates is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Number of COVID-19 vaccines in development by clinical phase

Table 1 COVID-19 Vaccines currently in use (Appendix)⁸

	BioNTech/ Pfizer BNT162b2	Beijing/ Sinopharm BBIBP-CorV	Moderna mRNA-1273
Where?	Approved in Canada, EU and other countries. Emergency use in U.K., U.S. and other countries. Approved for emergency use by WHO	Approved in China, U.A.E., Bahrain. Emergency use in Egypt	Approved in Canada. Emergency use in U.S., EU, Israel
Type	Messenger RNA Vaccines ⁹	Inactivated Coronavirus Vaccines ¹⁰	Messenger RNA Vaccines
How is it given?	2 doses, 3 weeks apart, intramuscular injection	2 doses, 3 weeks apart, intramuscular injection	2 doses, 4 weeks apart, intramuscular injection
What are its storage requirements?	Ultra-cold (-60°C to -80°C)	Pending - refrigeration (2°C to 8°C) is typical for inactivated vaccines	Refrigeration (2°C to 8°C) for up to 30 days or frozen (-15°C to -25°C) for long-term storage
Total number participating in registered trials	45,838	56,128	33,720
Efficacy data	Vaccine efficacy against COVID-19 reported to be 95% based on primary analysis of 170 confirmed cases	Vaccine efficacy against COVID-19 reported to be 79% but data are pending	Vaccine efficacy against COVID-19 reported to be 94.5% based on based on data on 95 cases

⁸ Information is taken from: COVID-19 vaccine tracker developed by the Vaccine Centre at the London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine (data updated to 1 January 2021) and WHO (data updated to January 10, 2021).

⁹ RNA and DNA vaccines represent a cutting-edge approach that uses genetically engineered RNA or DNA to generate a protein that itself safely prompts an immune response.

¹⁰ This type of vaccine consists of the disease-causing virus that has been inactivated or weakened (with heat or chemicals) so it does not cause disease but still it is able to generate an immune response. It can be used in people that may not be able to use a live attenuated virus vaccine (e.g., those who are immunocompromised).

INFORMATION & MISINFORMATION ABOUT COVID-19 VACCINATIONS

How do I make sense of all the COVID-19 vaccine information?

Since the emergence of the coronavirus pandemic in 2019, there has been a vast amount of information shared about the risk, protective actions and restrictions, and more recently about the COVID-19 vaccines. However, the amount of information and presence of contradictory information can make it difficult to decide what information to trust and whether to take the vaccine.

As countries across the globe roll out their vaccination programme, priority is typically being given to healthcare workers, people in a higher age group (e.g., over 70), and the clinically vulnerable. Information on priority groups and how and when you may have access to the vaccine may be available from your national government and public health authorities. Not everyone will share the same views of the vaccine and there are some people who may choose not to have the vaccine. However, it is important that any information covering the COVID-19 vaccine is clear and can be understood to enable people to make an informed decision.

Information on the COVID-19 vaccine will be available from a variety of different sources. This will include both different organisations (e.g., government, public health authorities, the media, community leaders, etc) and different channels (e.g., websites, social media such as Twitter or Facebook, television, printed materials, etc). Information may cover:

- The development and testing of the vaccine
- The roll-out of the vaccine to different groups
- The benefits and risks of having the vaccine
- Advice for particular groups such as pregnant women
- How you will receive the vaccine (e.g., number of doses)
- The effectiveness of the vaccine
- Side effects of the vaccine
- COVID-19 myths and correcting inaccurate information

There may be groups of the public that are unable to access the information available for different reasons such as not having access to online information and the information being available in limited languages and formats (e.g., not being available in audio or large print). If there are members of your family and friends who are unable to access information on the COVID-19 vaccine, please do share any facts with them. As the next section highlights, the COVID-19 pandemic has also witnessed an overwhelming amount of false information.

How do I know what information to trust?

According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), the COVID-19 pandemic has been accompanied by an *infodemic*¹¹. An infodemic describes the fast spread of a both misinformation and factual information, resulting in an overabundance of information.

Especially the rapid development and distribution of vaccines have been accompanied by a large amount of misinformation, myths and conspiracy theories. Misinformation is harmful in several ways: it endangers democracy, public health, and even the lives of individuals. However, there are simple ways to ‘flatten the curve of the infodemic’. The EU-funded H2020 project EUNOMIA¹² has defined guidelines for *Information Hygiene* that are simple and easy to apply by everyone:

Be cautious of information forwarded to you through your network. Because we tend to trust our friends, our cognitive filters weaken, making a social media feed fertile ground for misinformation, disinformation and ‘fake news’ to sneak into our consciousness.

Be wary of popular posts. Misinformation travels significantly faster, deeper and more broadly than the truth. Posts from individuals or organisations that are experts in a topic are not necessarily popular in social media.

Be wary of language that is making you feel emotional. It is designed to become viral, not to inform. Online content that evokes high-arousal emotions such as anger and anxiety has been shown to spread faster and more broadly than neutral content. Misinformation often uses inflammatory and sensational language, which may alter people’s emotions.

Be mindful of your emotions when reading a post. Anger makes you susceptible to biases. Anger encourages biased evaluation information, while anxiety promotes initial beliefs based on the information environment. Heightened emotionality is predictive of increased belief in misinformation.

Refrain from sharing based only on headline. Already reading a false statement once is enough to increase later perceptions of its accuracy (‘illusory truth effect’). The effect holds true even if participants forget having seen the information previously. Even if people disagree with information, repetition made it more plausible.

¹¹ WHO (2020). *Managing the COVID-19 infodemic: Promoting healthy behaviours and mitigating the harm from misinformation and disinformation*. Retrieved from <https://www.who.int/news/item/23-09-2020-managing-the-covid-19-infodemic-promoting-healthy-behaviours-and-mitigating-the-harm-from-misinformation-and-disinformation> (14.01.2021)

¹² EUNOMIA User-oriented, secure, trustful & decentralised social media, project funded under Grant Agreement No. 825171. <https://eunomia.social/>

Take a moment to think when provided with a nudge, such as some form of flag.

Most people do not want to spread misinformation, but the social media context focuses their attention on factors other than truth and accuracy. Flagging misinformation is most effective if a warning is shown even before reading misinformation, e.g. in the form of a tag that marks the information as suspect.

Be wary of resharing information for its high novelty.

Misinformation not only travels faster than true information, it is also more novel. Novel information is more likely to be retweeted, because novelty attracts human attention, contributes to productive decision-making, and encourages information sharing.

Repost to refute with evidence.

When resharing a post with a comment aiming to discredit it, we may still be contributing to its amplification. To be effective, corrections must explain why the misinformation was disseminated in the first place or provide an alternative explanation of the relevant information.

Use a dedicated tool or button to flag misinformation.

Users are generally more likely to believe articles that agree with their point of view. Asking users to rate articles pushes them to think more critically about the truthfulness of the articles.

**All in all, our recommendation is:
If in doubt, don't share.**

CORRECTING COVID-19 VACCINE MYTHS

In the following, we provide factual information that addresses the most popular myths related to COVID-19 vaccines¹³.

The vaccination is safe, it was rigorously tested and went through all necessary trials. There are reasons why the vaccination was developed so quickly: funding was no obstacle, there was a worldwide joint effort by scientists, and a lot of people volunteered to participate in clinical trials. The vaccine approval processes are also transparent.

Overview of registered clinical trials.

Hack MD. The COVID-19 Vaccine Development Process.

The mRNA vaccination cannot alter a person's DNA. Like any other vaccine, mRNA vaccines teach our immune systems to recognise and respond to the virus. The cells in our body read the genetic code – our DNA – and creates temporary genetic instructions – RNA – which tell the body how to produce the proteins they need to grow and repair. Once the proteins are created, the RNA is degraded. There is no evidence that this process can damage our own cells.

How mRNA Vaccines Work - Simply Explained.

Key facts about the COVID-19 vaccines.

European Vaccination Information Portal. How vaccines work.

The vaccination does not contain a tracking device nor a microchip. It is also not used by the government to control the general population.

Information about the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation's donation towards the development of a vaccine.

¹³ This information represents the state of knowledge as of January 2021

It is beneficial to get vaccinated even with a prior COVID-19 infection. Currently, we do not know if or for how long after infection someone is protected from getting COVID-19 again. Early evidence suggests natural immunity from COVID-19 may not last very long, but more studies are needed to better understand this. Due to the severe effects COVID-19 can have, and the possibility of re-infection, a vaccination is recommended.

European Medicines Agency. COVID-19 vaccines: key facts.

The COVID-19 vaccine is not harmful and will not lead to long-term side effects. Inflammation at the injection site or a day or two of side effects such as headaches mean the vaccine is working. Serious side effects (allergic reactions) are extremely rare.

European Vaccination Information Centre.

Hack MD. The potential side effects of COVID-19 vaccines.

Despite the vaccination, physical distancing and face masks are still important measures. Because we do not yet know if it is possible to spread the disease once vaccinated, even vaccinated people will need to wear masks and follow physical distancing rules. Further evaluations will assess the effect of the vaccine in preventing asymptomatic infection.

WHO. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19): Herd immunity, lockdowns and COVID-19.

The vaccine neither causes COVID-19 infections nor does it lead to positive test results. The vaccinations do not contain a live virus. Vaccinations sometimes cause fever or other mild side effects. That does not mean, however, that a person is infected. The vaccination may lead to positive antibody tests, which indicates a level of protection against the virus.

European Commission. Separating fact from fiction on COVID-19.

The vaccine does not cause infertility in women. No influence of COVID-19 nor the vaccination on fertility have been observed. It is also not believed to have an influence on pregnant or breastfeeding women. However, pregnant women are sometimes still advised to not take a vaccine until further research has been carried out.

Harvard Health Publishing. Wondering about COVID-19 vaccines if you're pregnant or breastfeeding?

There was no fetal tissue used to develop the vaccine. Some vaccines require the production of viruses, which can only replicate with the help of living host cells. While certain viruses for vaccines, such as some COVID-19 vaccine candidates, are produced using human fetal-derived cells, these cells and most of their genetic material are removed during the purification process and are therefore not present in the vaccine. Any residual DNA is also broken down into fragments during the purification process, which are harmless and do not affect our DNA.

Health Feedback. Although fetal-derived cells are used to grow viruses for some COVID-19 vaccines, the cells are not part of the vaccines.

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<https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019>

First lessons learned from COVID-19 vaccination in Spain

To illustrate the challenges public authorities may encounter, we showcase first lessons learned in the vaccination process in Spain.

In Spain, as in other countries, a vaccination plan has been developed in different phases, prioritizing vaccination for certain population groups based on risk. Until now, state bodies and security forces have collaborated in managing logistics.

However, specific incidents have occurred in the distribution and administration of vaccines that we have to learn from so that they are not repeated:

1. Administration to relatives of the people of the group to which they were directed, affecting the criteria of distributive justice.
2. Lack of training of the health worker administering the vaccine, which has led some people to receive the entire vial instead of the fraction corresponding to an individual dose.
3. Inability to administer all the vaccines due to excess doses arriving or because the number of people estimated or committed did not turn up to be vaccinated. In the case of the Pfizer/BioNtech vaccine, this implies the loss of the vaccines.

Most likely the first two have been isolated incidents that, with adequate control, training and information have a low risk of reoccurring. Regarding the third, it is necessary to dedicate sufficient personnel to the coordination tasks between the centre where the vaccines are administered and the logistics warehouse where they are stored. There will be a much higher risk of vaccine loss when vaccinating other risk groups such as the elderly, or people with chronic diseases that are self-employed and live at home, and who, for various reasons, might not attend their appointment in the vaccination centre.

To optimize the delivery of vaccines, there is a need for better coordination in distribution and storage. A fast and efficient vaccination plan is crucial for coming out of the COVID-19 pandemic, making vaccine delivery logistics a top priority and a shared concern amongst EU members.

To learn more about the vaccination campaign in Spain, read our [blog post](#), where one of the consortium partners, SAMUR-Protección Civil – a pre-hospital emergency – service, outlines the issues that public authorities encountered with the launch of the vaccination program in Spain.

The COVINFORM project

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Consortium	SYNYO GmbH (SYNYO) , Austria Magen David Adom in Israel (MDA) , Israel Samur Proteccion Civil (SAMUR) , Spain Universita Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC) , Italy SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (SINUS) , Germany Trilateral Research LTD (TRI UK) , UK Trilateral Research LTD (TRI IE) , Ireland Kentro Meleton Asfaleias – Center for Security Studies (KEMEA) , Greece Factor Social Consultoria em Psicossociologia e Ambiente LDA (FS) , Portugal Austrian Red Cross (AUTRC) , Austria Media Diversity Institute (MDI) , UK Societatea Națională de Cruce Rosie Din România – Romanian Red Cross (SNCR) , Romania University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN) , Belgium Sapienza University of Rome (SAPIENZA) , Italy University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC) , Spain Swansea University (SU) , UK Gotenborg University (UGOT) , Sweden
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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**COVID-19 vaccination
campaign in COVINFORM
countries: infographics &
best practices**

Bi-Monthly Report: 02

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The successful implementation of COVID-19 vaccination campaigns has been pointed out to be the only exit strategy from the pandemic. At the end of the first three months since the beginning of the vaccination efforts in COVINFORM countries, with this report we aim to provide a snapshot of the campaign deployment in each country through infographics providing detailed indicators related to the number of vaccinations and to the attitudes of the population about vaccination. Further, we aim to provide a brief report on the vaccination campaign in one of the COVINFORM countries:

Israel. The COVID-19 vaccination campaign of Israel has been widely recognized as one of the most effective around the world. Thus, it is relevant to get new insights about the strategy adopted by Israel to implement the COVID-19 vaccination campaign, by relying on the direct experience and testimony of Magen David Adom (MDA) in Israel, one of the partners of COVINFORM. In order to do so, we present both a brief report written by Itamar Laist (MDA) and an interview with Chaim Rafalowski (MDA) on the vaccination campaign in Israel.

VACCINATIONS IN COVINFORM COUNTRIES

By the end of December 2020, COVID-19 vaccination efforts began in COVINFORM countries: vaccination campaigns started on the 8th of December in the UK, on the 20th December in Israel and between the 26th and 31st December 2020 in most European countries. Plans for the deployment of the COVID-19 vaccine identifying the main vaccination strategies (including the selection of priority groups by phase of implementation, as well as key elements of the logistics of implementation) have been developed by countries at the national level.

As vaccination campaigns progress at different paces in countries represented in the COVINFORM project, we provide an Infographic focusing on the main indicators related to the roll out of the vaccination campaigns.

VACCINE UPTAKE IN COVINFORM COUNTRIES

Total number of vaccinations over time in COVINFORM countries

COVID-19 vaccine total doses administered in COVINFORM countries

These two graphs show the total number of COVID-19 vaccination doses administered in COVINFORM countries. In particular, the first graph presents the evolution over time of the doses administered since the beginning of the vaccination campaign in December 2020 to mid-March 2021 and the second graph the total number of vaccination doses administered the 16 March 2021. This is counted as a single dose, therefore, is different from the total number of people vaccinated, taking into account that people receive multiple doses.

Share of population who received at least one dose of COVID-19 vaccine

This map shows the share of the total population in COVINFORM countries that has received at least one dose of the COVID-19 vaccine.

Total number of people who have been fully vaccinated against COVID-19 in COVINFORM countries

The graph shows the total number of people fully vaccinated against COVID-19 in each COVINFORM country at mid-March 2021.

Share of population fully vaccinated against COVID-19

This graph presents the share of the population fully vaccinated against COVID-19 (calculated as the ratio of the people fully vaccinated in each country to the total population of each country) in COVINFORM countries at mid-March 2021.

Cumulative uptake full vaccination
in the COVINFORM countries **4,7%**

Cumulative uptake first dose
in the COVINFORM countries **15,4%**

Progress in vaccine uptake in COVINFORM countries

Daily COVID-19 vaccine doses administered per 100 people in COVINFORM countries

The table and the graphs above show respectively the percentage of the population resident in COVINFORM countries who received at least one dose and who was fully vaccinated against COVID-19 until mid-March 2021, the way to go to reach the objective of 70% of people fully vaccinated, and the number of COVID-19 vaccine doses administered per 100 people (7-day average per 100 people of the total population in the week 10-16 March 2021).

VACCINATION OF VULNERABLE POPULATION

COVID-19 vaccination campaigns in COVINFORM countries are designed in order to give priority in the vaccine distributions to the most vulnerable populations. Although all the COVINFORM countries are following this approach, there are some relevant differences in the definition of vulnerable population. For instance, some countries has defined as vulnerable population the health practitioners, thus they have to be vaccinated in the first phase of the vaccination campaign, while other countries have not. Here we present the figures of the COVID-19 vaccination campaign for people aged 80 and above: this category of the population has been recognized as vulnerable (because of age) in all the COVINFORM countries.

Culmulative uptake (%) of the first dose in people aged 80 years and above iin some COVINFORM countries

Culmulative uptake (%) of full vaccinations in people aged 80 years and above in some COVINFORM countries

The two maps above represent respectively the percent of the people aged 80 and over (over the population of this age group) that received one dose of COVID-19 vaccines and that has been fully vaccinated in COVINFORM countries.

ATTITUDES ON VACCINATION

As we have stressed at the very beginning of this report, a successful COVID-19 vaccination campaign is the essential way out from the pandemic. Availability of the vaccines and attitudes toward vaccination are the two major barriers to managing the COVID-19 pandemic in the long-term. While the national states are responsible for making the vaccines available to their population, the individual attitudes toward vaccination are the most important indicator of the population willingness to respond positively to the vaccination campaigns adopted by the government, knowing that the vaccination is not mandatory. Here we present for some COVINFORM countries the results of a survey exploring people's behaviors and attitudes in response to COVID-19, realized by the Imperial College London. People were asked about their willingness of being vaccinated against COVID-19. The survey is repeated each month; therefore we can see the evolution of the people response to the vaccination campaign over time.

Attitudes on vaccinations in some COVINFORM countries: % who would get a vaccine if available

The chart above shows the attitudes on vaccinations against COVID-19 in some COVINFORM countries. Data were collected monthly starting from November 2020 by a survey exploring people's behaviors and attitudes in response to COVID-19 realized by the Imperial College London and are available through the YouGov COVID-19 Behaviour Tracker Data Hub.

BEST PRACTICE: THE COVID-19 VACCINATION IN ISRAEL

After the BioNTech/Pfizer vaccine against COVID-19 was approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and European Medicines Agency (EMA), it was approved to be used in Israel by the Ministry of Health, the Israeli government initiated a vaccination campaign on December 20th, 2020. The BioNTech/Pfizer vaccine is the only vaccine given in Israel, and it is given twice (with the same dose) for each individual, 21 days between the doses. In the beginning, it was not recommended for people who recovered from COVID-19 to be vaccinated, but research showed that the antibodies level for recovered patients is lower than the one of vaccinated people, so now it is recommended for them to be vaccinated with one dose only three months after they recovered.

WHAT CATEGORIES OF POPULATION WERE PRIORITIZED?

As the number of available vaccines at the beginning of the campaign was limited, only people older than 60 years old or first-line health care personnel were able to be vaccinated. The first two persons to be vaccinated were the Prime Minister and the Minister of Health, both older than 60 and therefore entitled to the vaccine, to encourage the public to trust the vaccine. When the vaccine supply grew, more age groups were able to be vaccinated starting with persons 55 years and older, pregnant women (due to the peak of seriously ill pregnant women, most probably due to the effect of the British variant), then youth age 16-18 (in order to allow them to reengage in face to face classes before the final exams), followed by the rest of the population. Youth under the age of 18 (16-18) years old need to have one of their parents present or bring with them a signed approval from their parents.

All the people living in Israel are entitled to vaccination (including irregular migrants). Palestinians, living in the Palestinian territory, with working permits in Israel, are vaccinated with MODERNA vaccines.

The details of the contracts are a commercial secret, including the price and the quantities.

The Israeli Ministry of Health publicly announced that the government has enough vaccines, and two doses are secured to all those who are eligible.

THE DEPLOYMENT OF THE VACCINATION CAMPAIGN AND THE ROLE PLAYED BY MAGEN DAVID ADOM

The vaccination operation run by the Ministry of Health, targeting some six million people aged 16 and older as "eligible for vaccination", out of about 9,3 million inhabitants. The operation is based on two types of vaccination models- fixed sites and mobile sites. In the fixed sites the vaccination is done by the four Health Maintenance Organizations (HMO, to which all Israelis are affiliated under the mandatory medical insurance law), who are vaccinating more than 90% of the population. These sites include locations like the HMOs clinics, hospitals, shopping malls (that were closed during the lockdown), sports stadiums, convention centers, and other similar locations. The vaccines are given by nurses and emergency medical technicians (EMT). The mobile sites run by Magen David Adom (The Israeli National Society, member of the International Movement of Red Cross and Red Crescent, and the National Pre-hospital Care provider), giving their EMTs duly trained the authorization to administer the vaccine.

Firstly, Magen David Adom (MDA) was tasked to vaccinate all the population living in long-term care facilities and the staff there, an operation completed within seven weeks with the second dose administered to all the residents and staff.

Later MDA was tasked with organizing vaccination campaigns in communities with low vaccination rates, vaccination sites for irregular migrants, followed by workplaces, and in coordination with local authorities in places with large public convergence. On one occasion, MDA vaccinated during a festival in a nature reserve. Magen David Adom is using specially built trailers with refrigerators for this task.

The mobile campaigns created significant public attention, especially a campaign with Tel Aviv Jaffa municipality, where young people are vaccinated in pubs, and in Jerusalem's largest market.

For the HMOs vaccination sites, one needs to register for vaccinating. For most of the mobile sites, no registration is needed and people can simply walk in. After the first dose of the vaccine is given, an appointment for the second one is scheduled for 21 days later (or 28 days for MODERNA vaccines).

To date (March 14th, 2021), 5,129,901 people were vaccinated in Israel with the first dose of the vaccine, and 4,134,860 people received both doses. MDA vaccinated 397,954 persons with the first dose and 212,511 with a second dose. MDA uses a dedicated IT system to manage the operation, send text messages for the appointments and transfer the data in a secured format to the MoH.

Since the vaccination campaign began, a significant decrease in numbers of new cases and severe cases is demonstrated. This decrease is more significant among people older than 60 years old (an age group with a great majority of vaccinated people). Among the hospitalized patients, almost all were not vaccinated.

Magen David Adom, being a grass root, community-based organization mobilizes its volunteers, representing different groups in the Israeli society, to campaign in favor of the vaccines, explain the importance to the person and the benefit to the society, and to fight against rumors and vaccination hesitancy. We can see the positive impact of the person-to-person approach used by the volunteers. Magen David Adom, an organization proudly serving our society for more than 90 years, is proud to be part of the global fight against COVID 19, and lending a shoulder to protect our society against the pandemic.

INTERVIEW WITH CHAIM RAFALOWSKI, DISASTER MANAGEMENT AND EU PROJECTS COORDINATOR, MAGEN DAVID ADOM IN ISRAEL

Elena Ambrosetti and Marina Zannella conducted an interview with Chaim Rafalowski on Israel's vaccination programme.

Data Sources

Austria Ministry of Health

European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control

Government of Israel

Government of Romania

Government of the United Kingdom

Greece Ministry of Health

Imperial College London YouGov Covid 19 Behaviour Tracker Data Hub

Ministry of Health of Spain

National COVID-19 vaccine deployment plans in the EU27 member countries

National Health Service of Portugal

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OurWorldinData

Public Health Agency of Sweden

Robert Koch Institut

Sciensano via covid-vaccinatie.be

The COVINFORM project

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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**A Glimpse of the
Lessons Learned During
the COVID-19 Pandemic**

Bi-Monthly Report: 03

Authors

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BOTTOM LINE

National governments, public health decision-makers and experts, and non-governmental organizations were witnessed as communicators of COVID-19 statistics, advice, and advocacy. These stakeholders were seen to be effective by delivering constant communication to the public to alleviate concerns, yet some criticism has been levied for misinformation and the presentation of what some have referred to as “fake news”. These stakeholders should prepare their constituents with the response framework of a crisis or pandemic that is concise and simple to follow. Implementing resiliency into a pandemic response is complex but an effective communication strategy stimulates a resilient outcome.

In this report, the global methods for communication during the COVID-19 pandemic are discussed. Lessons learned from the communication vehicles are witnessed, leading to best practices and guidelines for improved communication in the future.

GLOBAL METHODS FOR COMMUNICATION...

This bi-monthly report summarises the findings and best practices of an extensive desk-based research activity of communication practices. As outcome, a synthetic description of COVID-19 communication strategies and practices by governments and public health authorities in 15 countries in the EU and beyond has been elaborated.

The 15 countries considered were: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Israel, Ireland, Italy, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom and United States of America. These countries each have their own communication processes, yet similarities exist. The communication analysis are presented from the lenses of national governments, public health decision-makers and experts, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The following sub-sections explore the nuances and similarities between communication platforms below.

... from national governments

Only four countries created a formal communication strategy at the national level. The remaining countries either had no strategy or their strategy was sparse. Similarity occurred for every country when top-level governmental offices acted as the primary voice. In general, these voices were either presidents or prime ministers/chancellors. Internal security officials were also seen to have speaking roles in some countries, and Spain also witnessed experts and data technicians as impactful voices.

While these governmental bodies set the vision for guidelines and future goals for the pandemic, the mission of communication was left to outside health entities. For example, communicating the measures for protecting oneself from the pandemic for every individual and stakeholder type (elderly, migrants, and disabled, for example) was the job of outside health entities. Governmental communication reverberated the advice of health professionals, encouraging safe physical distancing, mask-wearing, hand washing, and also considered the reopening of economies.

... from public health decision-makers and experts

Six countries had formal communication agendas set in place for public health decision-makers and experts. The targeted audience of these decision-makers were health professionals, education professionals, leaders of different economic sectors, and eligible candidates for the vaccine. Some countries, such as the UK and Sweden, targeted minority populations such as refugees and migrants more than other countries. Germany opened a communication forum amongst differing professionals, such as epidemiologists and practitioners. Spain was witnessed to target at-risk populations. These examples have in common the sharing of information on how to prevent the spread of the pandemic for different stakeholders.

Recommendations for preventing the spread of the pandemic were grounded by statistics from these public health decision-makers. The statistics included cases, hospitalizations, and deaths to inform governmental bodies about testing, vaccinations, travel recommendations, and opportunities for financial assistance.

... from non-governmental organizations (NGOs)

A wide range of NGOs were witnessed to represent at-risk populations as well as minority groups. Several countries translated the pandemic statistics to affected stakeholders and the NGOs acted as a vehicle for communication to those at risk or affected. For example, in the UK, the Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic family pandemic hotline was created to assist individuals that represent those minorities aged eleven and up.

From the professional standpoint, labor, economic, and professional organizations provided considerations for how the workforce must adapt to the pandemic and the considerations for another crisis. For some companies, the need for an adapted work environment was made clear in public announcements.

Public health non-governmental organizations worked to gain money and support for everyone impacted by the pandemic. Mental health issues gained notoriety during the pandemic and organizations such as the Red Cross, UNICEF, and Save the Children developed campaigns for mental health among other necessities such as blood donation and online school. Disabled individuals were also targeted by organizations such as the National Associations of Families of People with Intellectual and/or Relational Disabilities.

Political and socioeconomic concerns were also addressed by organizations. For example, in Germany, human rights, freedom of speech, freedom of religion, and protest as it related to the pandemic were addressed. These addresses also lumped in the existence of misinformation surrounding these political tenets.

LESSONS FOR COMMUNICATION

Methods for dealing with uncertainty for the pandemic is vital for a country's communication platform. A main trend in the countries evaluated in this report are that open and transparent messages were relayed with the most accurate data available. Sometimes this came with consequences, such as the uncertainty around mask-wearing early during the pandemic.

In general, the constant flow of information to citizens was positively accepted by citizens. While information was withheld at the beginning of the pandemic, the transparency was witnessed to increase as more research and facts were found about how the virus is transmitted. In all 15 countries different entities and organizations have taken charge of publishing this information with little overlap, which slowed the passing of information early during the pandemic.

Daily press conferences and the use of social media by governmental bodies to relay information about the pandemic was seen to be positive. The same conferences and social media platforms used by health experts was also seen to be commendable and relevancy was witnessed. Information flowing from public speakers attaining to more trusted parties was followed more closely than from politicians, in general. While press conferences can be quite antiquated, this communication platform was witnessed to be quite successful at relaying important messages. Social media made these messages even more accessible to all parties and aided with fact-checking.

However, timing, clarity, and uncertainty in the research proved to be difficult for communicators. Mass media was seen to be inaccurate at times, causing confusion. The timeliness of the data was criticized, generating mistrust and further confusion. Furthermore, this presented the opportunity of misinformation to surface, compounding the effects of confused parties.

An uncertainty with the relation between governmental and non-governmental bodies sparked confusion as well. These bodies used different communication strategies, with some being more or less inclusive of information than others. Overarching organizations have autonomy to present information, which was poorly understood by the public. This led to the creation of misinformation, or "fake news" as some countries coined the phrase. In Spain, the correlation between individuals with an interest in the idea of "fake news" was seen to increase COVID-19 related deaths.

While many lessons learned on the communication front can be garnered, an important takeaway is the need for transparent, frequent communication that connects research to real-life scenarios. Findings were bolstered when differing agencies or organizations shared similar datasets. Timely messages about these findings to the public was witnessed to have a positive response for the majority of people.

BEST PRACTICES AND GUIDELINES...

As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, many lessons learned were gathered from top-level executives to the common person. These lessons learned can be compiled temporally into two sections: before the pandemic and during the pandemic, as highlighted in the below sections of this report.

... before the pandemic

While this is complex to achieve, governments must realize that risk communication is required ahead of a crisis. This risk communication process bolsters a country's resilience during each part of the cycle seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1 – Steps to resilience from a crisis for a country as presented by the RESILENS project

Before	During	After
Learn	Respond	Learn
Prepare	Mitigage	Transform
Prevent	Adapdt	Adapt
Protect	Learn	Recover

Resilience and safety culture should be placed at the forefront for decision-makers before a crisis takes place. These two concepts can prepare the critical infrastructure that is required to manage a pandemic (UNISDR, 2015). During these stages, risk communication must consider the nature of risks and risk perception (Slovic, 2000; Covello & Sandman, 2001; Paek & Hove, 2017), the risk culture of target populations (Dressel, 2015), and promote prevention and science (Marec & Schiele, 2018; Petras, Israelashvili & Miller, 2020; Sloboda & David, 2020). This enhances public media and information literacy, which can prevent misinformation. Since the use of smartphones and technology is prevalent in today's society, bits of media education for the public can help target misinformation at the source to prevent the infiltration of misinformation.

The risk communication strategy must consider the following (Cabinet Office, 2012):

1. The public perception of information and how people will respond, understand, and react to emergency information
2. Timely details up front with more in-depth information to follow
3. Informing the public of the imminent actions to take, the responders' actions to assist recovery, and the actions the public should take to reduce the impact of the crisis itself

Governments must be active stakeholders throughout this process. Basic questions of the crisis should be answered directly with the most recognizable office conveying the details. This governmental body must synthesize available information to package it into the essential takeaways for the possibility of a crisis.

A process for stakeholder engagement must also take place for transparency and accessibility to information. This stems from the levels of community engagement presented by EDCD (2020) that summarizes engagement into five synchronous categories: outreach, consultation, involvement, collaboration, and shared leadership. In other words, invigorating stakeholders with information creates a sense of teamwork such that an individual agent can trust the system that he or she embodies. Ataguba & Ataguba (2020) summarize this process further:

1. Set up and strengthen risk communication systems
2. Strengthening internal coordination to recognize inherent strengths
3. Timely and effective communication to give public health advice
4. Active community engagement that is inclusive of all stakeholders
5. Addressing uncertainty and misinformation
6. Capacity assessment as the situation evolves

... during pandemics

Once a pandemic or crisis occurs, tangible action must have already occurred to optimize resiliency. Since communication is a vast responsibility and requirement, it is imperative that a structure is nominated to coordinate, plan, and monitor the communication responses. A coordinator is an individual that assumes the role of coalescing stakeholders to allow for communication. This central coordinator must be knowledgeable of the crisis and should be in constant contact with the decision-maker for the crisis. To manage the crisis, it is important that the communication system:

- Maintains strong leadership nationally and within local groups
- Identifies community leaders
- Creates opportunities for engagement, such as through interactive forums for the public to ask questions

Messages relayed from these coordinators must be relevant at all times. Their recommendations must be actionable, grounded in factual evidence, and consequences of not following their recommendations must be identified. This coordinator must speak in simple language to be easily understood and use a variety of techniques to adequately convey the necessary message. These messages should be phrased how the public best receives messages: in a narrative style (Ngai, Singh, & Koon, 2020).

Acknowledging uncertainty is essential. Information must not be withheld for fear of how the public will respond because trust with and for the public takes time. Consistent messages prevent speculation, such as through timely social media updates.

Information to targeted audiences must come from credible and trusted sources. While no strategy is perfect at finding the best individual, agency, or office to be the spokesperson, it may be effective to find role models at the local level to take on the responsibility for a more localized approach. These individuals can be medical professionals, scientists, public communicators, or even religious leaders. These individuals can use multiple channels to coordinate information, such as:

- Traditional mass media (TV, radio, and newspapers)
- Official channels and groups
- Text alerts
- Social media

Throughout this display of information, it is important to monitor public feedback. In this way, this enables the modification of messages to suit the public optimally. Furthermore, the information cycle must also be monitored for the media to ensure that the televised, printed, or broadcasted information represents accurate data and findings.

CONCLUSION

Communication is essential for pandemic response. Communication has been coordinated during the COVID-19 response by governmental bodies, public health decision-makers and experts, and non-governmental organizations. For future response to a crisis or pandemic, it is important for these spokespeople to deliver coordinated, transparent,

accessible, and timely information to the public. A clear structure should be delineated for which office or body will be responsible with giving recommendations for health and economic policy. Risk of a pandemic or crisis should be communicated before one begins and resilience must be bolstered through effective communication strategies.

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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**COVID-19:
Findings on the
Governmental Responses
in COVINFORM countries**

Bi-Monthly Report: 04

Authors

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INTRODUCTION

This bi-monthly report summarizes the findings of the desk-based research that was conducted for the purposes of WP4 in the COVINFORM Project. An overall view of the Institutional and Government responses in the 14 target countries will be provided in conjunction with several visuals.

INSTITUTIONS AND THEIR RESPONSE TIMELINE

At the dawn of 2020, International Institutions and National Governments were up against the unprecedented COVID-19 health crisis. A coordinated response at all political levels was deemed necessary in order to ensure the safety of the society. Internationally, the World Health Organisation (WHO), the United Nations (UN) and the European Union (EU) mobilized their mechanisms to contain the spread of the virus, inform the public and provide guidance to the state Governments. The WHO provided continuous advice and technical consultation regarding health protocols and surveillance while actively responding to the crisis by issuing its **Strategic Preparedness and Response Plan (SPRP)**¹. An all-around response was also employed by the UN and its “**Comprehensive Response to COVID-19 Saving Lives, Protecting Societies, Recovering Better**”² document, which addressed socio-economic issues such as Peacekeeping, Tourism, Education, and others. The European Union’s

actions, alongside Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), were also proven to be pivotal in dealing with the pandemic. Political measures were taken by the Union to tackle the consequences at all action areas of the EU. A **COVID-19 response team** was set up by Commission President Ursula von der Leyen to coordinate responses to the crisis, while policies were implemented to raise capital for financial assistance, research, crisis management, solidarity, and digitalization of services³. Lately, the EU has also focused in promoting vaccinations and ensuring universal access to the available vaccines by raising €15.9 billion for middle and low-income countries⁴, funding additional research programs such as COVINFORM in order not only to address the behavioural, social and economic impacts of the outbreak response, but to ensure a cohesive recovery plan for Europe.

¹ World Health Organization (2021). COVID-19 Strategic Preparedness and Response Plan (SPRP 2021). Retrieved May 26,2021 from [here](#)

² [see here](#)

³ European Commission. (n.d.). European Commission's coronavirus response team. Retrieved May 26 2021, from [here](#)

⁴ European Commission. (n.d.) Safe and Effective Vaccination. Public Health. Retrieved May, 26, 2021, from [here](#)

WHO Declares COVID-19 as a Public Health Emergency.

30.01.2020

01.02.2020

Flight restrictions from EU countries.

WHO Issues Strategic Preparedness and Response Plan.

04.02.2020

24.02.2020

The European Commission announces a new aid package of €232 million (\$252 million) for global preparedness and response to COVID-19.

Creation of the European Response Team.

02.03.2020

09.03.2020

First European Nationwide Lockdown in Italy. Lockdowns are imposed in European countries throughout March.

A handful of European countries begin to ease restrictions.

13.04.2020

06.2020

UN issues its Comprehensive Response to COVID-19 Plan.

COVID-19 infections in Europe are back to levels seen in March. European countries announce new restrictions after cases spike.

09.2020

12.2020

EMA approves Pfizer's vaccine for COVID-19.

Israel begins its vaccination campaign with Israeli Prime Minister being vaccinated live on TV.

12.2020

01.2021

European Countries purchase doses of vaccines. Vaccination Campaigns begin in European Countries. UK starts vaccinations with Astra-Zeneca.

GOVERNMENTAL RESPONSES ON NATIONAL LEVEL

“Man is by nature a political animal”⁵ (Aristotle 385-322 BC), and he strives to form societies functioning properly under accountable, transparent, responsive, and fair governments. Particularly during crisis times, such as COVID-19 pandemic, a strong and well-elaborated plan not only on an international, but also on a national level was required to provide a coordinated response to the current health emergency. The desktop research of COVINFORM project has been conducted to 14 countries as depicted in Figure 1.

As Table 1 reveals, despite the fact that all 14 countries have administrative differences in their governmental structures, the majority of them have adopted a centralized approach on the strategy and the relevant responses adopted against COVID-19 pandemic, with all core decisions coming from their central government. Eight of them declared their State in an Emergency situation “stricto sensu” taking into consideration to respect the relevant human rights as outlined in their Constitution and the international legislature, while all of them adopted specific emergency measures, laws, and mechanisms to properly and timely respond to the health crisis, relying also on their existing mechanisms against crises with major or minor adaptations.

Figure 1: COVINFORM 14 Countries under research (desktop)

⁵ Barnes, J. (2000). Aristotle: A Very Short Introduction. Oxford Paperbacks.

Table 1: Comparison among 14 countries under research relevant to COVID-19 measures⁶

Country	Governmental Structure	Declaration of State of Emergency "Stricto Sensu" (Constitutionally)	Declaration of Emergency in the form of 'special powers' mechanisms and emergency Laws	Movement Restrictions	Physical Distancing and Masks
Austria	Federal Parliamentary Republic	No ⁷	Yes	Yes	Yes
Belgium	Constitutional Representative Monarchy	No ⁸	Yes	Yes	Yes
Cyprus	Presidential Republic	Yes ⁹	Yes	Yes	Yes
Germany	Federal Parliamentary Republic	No ¹⁰	Yes	Yes	Yes
Greece	Presidential Parliamentary Republic	Yes ¹¹	Yes	Yes	Yes
Ireland	Parliamentary Democracy	No ¹²	Yes	Yes	Yes
Israel	Parliamentary Democracy	Yes ¹³	Yes	Yes	Yes
Italy	Democratic Parliamentary Republic	Yes ¹⁴	Yes	Yes	Yes
Portugal	Semi-presidential Democratic Republic	Yes ¹⁵	Yes	Yes	Yes
Romania	Parliamentary republic with semi-presidential regime	Yes ¹⁶	Yes	Yes	Yes
Spain	Parliamentary Monarchy	Yes (<i>state of alarm</i>) ¹⁷	Yes	Yes	Yes
Sweden	Constitutional Monarchy	No ¹⁸	Yes (<i>in the form of recommendations</i>)	Yes	Yes
Switzerland	Federalist Political System	Yes ¹⁹	Yes	Yes	Yes
United Kingdom	Constitutional Monarchy and Parliamentary Democracy	No ²⁰	Yes	Yes	Yes

⁶ [see here](#) | ⁷ [see here](#) | ⁸ [see here](#) | ⁹ [see here](#) | ¹⁰ *Ibid* 7 | ¹¹ *Ibid* 8 | ¹² *Ibid* 8 | ¹³ [see here](#) | ¹⁴ *Ibid* 7 | ¹⁵ [see here](#) | ¹⁶ *Ibid* 6 | ¹⁷ *Ibid* 7 | ¹⁸ *Ibid* 14 | ¹⁹ [see here](#) | ²⁰ [see here](#)

More in particular, in **Austria** major responsibilities have been granted to the Ministry of Health²¹ inside of which a dedicated CORONA Taskforce²² had been created by health and social experts that provide scientific advice on the handling of the crisis. In **Belgium**, several bodies have been created²³ (Risk Assessment Group, Risk Management Group, Economic Risk Management Group and Expert Strategy Exit Group as well as a newly formed Consultative Committee), while in **Cyprus** the main actors were the Government and experts from the scientific community cooperating towards the pandemic²⁴. In **Germany**²⁵, the pre-existing Infection Protection Act, along with a National Pandemic Plan, and other relevant laws and guidelines have been activated, with the Lander Governments to be the ones to have the power to decide on the respective restrictions, on their local level independently. The **Greek** government activated the National Crisis Management Mechanism of the General Secretariat for Civil Protection²⁶ responsible to coordinate the general actions and agencies/committees relevant to tackle the pandemic. In **Ireland**²⁷, due to the elections that were conducted short before the pandemic outbreak, an initial subcommittee responsible for policy directions for the COVID-19 pandemic has been formed by the Department of Health, along with a Special Cabinet Committee and a National Public Health Emergency Team supported by an Expert Advisory Group as well as eleven sub-groups, on the combat of COVID-19. In **Israel**, a Special Commission for COVID-19 on a parliamentary level has been created since the beginning of the pandemic, with their powers to be transferred to the "Ministers Commission for

Facing COVID-19 and its Implications" (COVID-19 Cabinet)²⁸. The Civil Protection Department along with the Scientific Technical Committee (CTS) and other fifteen task forces have been introduced in **Italy**²⁹ working together with the Ministry of Health to lead and act against the health crisis. **Portuguese** government³⁰ structured a specific body from Governmental officials (Structure of Monitorization of the State of Emergency), along with other committees dedicated to the coordination and mobilization towards COVID-19 pandemic. In **Romania**³¹, all the medical decisions were taken based on emergency ordinances issued by the Romanian Government, with the assistance of relevant experts and specialists, while in **Spain**³², a new coordination structure named the Single Authority/ Command was initially introduced to lead and coordinate the responses to the COVID-19, which was later on replaced by multiple Delegate Authorities by the autonomous communities. In **Sweden**, there were no specific adaptations in the governmental structure prior or during COVID-19, while in **Switzerland** the Swiss Federal Council was given the power to make decisions for all the country³³, not needing to consolidate with the cantons, and it was enforced with two non-decisive scientific task forces. In the **United Kingdom**³⁴, all four nations adopted a joint response towards the pandemic, establishing new ministerial structures and four committees focusing on health, public sector preparedness, economy, and international response, replaced afterwards by the 'COVID-19 Strategy' and the 'COVID-19 Operations' cabinet.

²¹ [see here](#) | ²² [see here](#)

²³ Desson, Z., Weller, E., McMeekin, P., & Ammi, M. (2020). An analysis of the policy responses to the COVID-19 pandemic in France, Belgium, and Canada. *Health Policy and Technology*, 9(4), 430–446.

²⁴ Petridou, E., Zahariadis, N., & Ceccoli, S. (2020). Averting institutional disasters? Drawing lessons from China to inform the Cypriot response to the COVID-19 pandemic. *European Policy Analysis*, 6(2), 318-327

²⁵ [see here](#) | ²⁶ [see here](#) | ²⁷ [see here](#) | ²⁸ [see here](#)

²⁹ Sanfelici, M. (2020). The Italian response to the COVID-19 crisis: lessons learned and future direction in social development. *The Int Journal of Com and Soc Develop*, 2(2): 191-210.

³⁰ [see here](#) | ³¹ [see here](#) | ³² [see here](#)

³³ Eichenauer, V. and Sturm, J.-E. (2020). Die wirtschaftspolitischen Maßnahmen der Schweiz zu Beginn der COVID-19-Pandemie. *Perspektiven der Wirtschaftspolitik*, 21(3), pp. 290-300.

³⁴ [see here](#)

The adoption of specific movement suspensions (e.g., curfews, national and local lockdowns, suspension of business and education, etc.) has been one of the main measures against COVID-19 in all countries under research, with differentiations on the strictness of each measure based on the development of the pandemic on a national and/or local level. Effects on the people's economic situation due to the aforementioned restrictions, have urged governments to adopt certain long- and short-term measures for economic support and further financial incentives to the sectors that had been most hit by the pandemic.

VULNERABLE GROUPS

The research program (COVINFORM) identifies as vulnerable the groups of people that were affected (physically, economically, socially, and mentally) by the pandemic and the governmental responses to COVID-19, based on the terminology provided by the EU Migration and Home Affairs³⁵, European Institute for Gender Equality³⁶ and European Center

for Disease Prevention and Control³⁷. Vulnerable groups can include minors, unaccompanied minors, disabled people, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with minor children and persons who have been subjected to torture, rape, or other serious forms of psychological, physical, or sexual violence, victims of trafficking.

Table 2: Matrix with identified vulnerable groups across 14 countries.

Vulnerable groups	Austria	Belgium	Cyprus	Germany	Greece	Ireland	Israel	Ireland	Portugal	Romaina	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	UK
Elderly	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X
Migrants		X	X		X	X	X	X			X		X	X
Poor	X	X				X	X	X			X		X	X
Homeless		X									X	X		X
Children	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X		X
Women	X	X	X		X	X		X	X	X		X	X	X
People living with health vulnerabilities	X	X	X		X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X
People living with disabilities	X	X	X	X	X			X		X	X			X
Roma					X									X

³⁵see here | ³⁶see here | ³⁷see here

Overall, each country included in the analysis had a similar approach in their responses towards the pandemic and identified the elderly, citizens with chronic health-related issues, health-care workers and migrants as highly vulnerable groups. **Austria** focused around “at-risk groups”, emphasizing mainly on indicators such as (health): chronic diseases, diabetes, cancer, obesity, (social): disabled citizens, parental status, poverty, age, and single parents. **Belgium** had a well-rounded approach by establishing two specialized governmental bodies to address COVID-19 and vulnerable groups. Belgium’s approach also included parameters such as homeless, sex workers and migrants. In a similar manner, **Cyprus** focused on health-related vulnerable groups and the elderly, migrants, asylum seekers and inmates. **Germany** identified the elderly, disabled, employers, employees as well as victims of domestic violence or citizens that encountered psychological issues due to COVID-19 restrictions as vulnerable groups. **Greece** health-related needs more vulnerable than the general population. In **Ireland**, the government has focussed on health-related needs more vulnerable than the general population. In Ireland, the government has focussed on the protection of women, healthcare workers and Roma communities. The **Israeli** government focused on the elderly in health-care facilities, children as well as ultraorthodox Jewish and Arab societies. **Italy** also paid attention to protecting the elderly, victims of domestic violence, children, migrant groups, healthcare workers and minorities. In a similar manner, **Romania** and **Portugal** also focussed on the elderly and migrants. **Spain** adopted a well-rounded approach, providing special attention to health-related and social variables resulting in a solid response to protect vulnerable groups including elderly, migrants, single parents and

employees. **Sweden** predominately focused on the elderly and on vulnerable children, undocumented migrants, homeless people and victims of domestic violence. **Switzerland** tended the needs of the elderly as well as citizens with health-related needs. Concluding, the **United Kingdom’s** approach focused on the elderly, ethnic minorities, young citizens, victims of domestic abuse and homeless people.

The above-mentioned countries issued COVID-19 related laws which revolved around social distancing, funding, and administrative powers to protect more effectively vulnerable groups. In addition, COVID-19 dedicated bodies and agencies were tasked to monitor and address COVID-19 issues in relation to vulnerable citizens. The most common relief measures to help vulnerable groups were but not limited to the option to work and study from home, paid leaves, provision of necessary items (clothes, food, hygiene products) and protective equipment, psychological support, financial benefits, regular testing and disinfections, discount on basic commodities and bills. In conclusion, all countries have adopted COVID-19 prevention related policies and other measures based on the fluctuation and evolution of the pandemic in order to minimize the devastating impacts of the pandemic to the relevant populations.

COMMUNICATION PRACTICES

In times of emergency, communication is crucial. According to WHO³⁸, since the COVID-19 pandemic is evolving rapidly, communicators should adapt the messages in accordance with the fast evolution of the data in order to provide sufficient and effective information to the public.

In general, all countries included in the desk research created a quite similar communication campaign early in 2020, which changed during the pandemic as new data and new demands were identified. More precisely, the majority of the countries implemented a communication campaign which was a joint effort from public and private actors utilizing traditional and digital channels of communication. Thus, each campaign was disseminated through TV spots, radio, social media, print and outdoor advertisements, and in some cases as in the UK, the government sent letters to the public providing information and guidelines on how to protect themselves against getting infected by COVID-19, noting that apart from social media, all this communication has been one-way to some degree, without giving directly the chance to the public to directly comment or pose any questions or worries they might have. Informing and educating the public regarding COVID-19 was identified as a key element by the governments, thus, almost all countries created a 360° communication campaign to reach all age groups. Italy put great emphasis on social media since its communication campaign was mainly carried

via social media platforms as they also wanted to provide great levels of public communication and interaction. Finally, nowadays social communication reaches a wider audience than the traditional, hence it was largely used by all countries.

One critical communication element was to initially reach individuals at increased health risk, with later being expanded to other categories of vulnerable groups. Language barriers or special guidelines for vulnerable people came later in multiple countries or were created after incidents within those groups. However, all countries addressed that issue as the situation demanded. Additionally, daily briefings from governmental officials alongside with respected scientific/health experts have been adopted from almost all countries and are identified as a highly effective communication way to address the proper message to the public. Finally, all countries created official websites which included information, guidelines, news, frequently asked questions, and phone lines for psychological or practical support in order to be available any time for the public.

³⁸ [see here](#)

Regarding communication practices, almost all countries responded immediately and quite early in 2020 by launching 360° campaigns in order to inform, educate and protect the public during those times of uncertainty. By also implementing all means of communication, it was achieved to

interact and approach all age groups resulting in a successful communication scheme. The basic difference can be found on the levels of public trust on the communicator which was also shifted quite frequently during the pandemic waves.

Figure 2: Indicative communication material from Italy, Spain, Greece, Cyprus, UK, Ireland, Austria, Belgium

CONCLUSION

Efficient and timely decision-making is essential when dealing with a health crisis. It is not an understatement to say that the established political system was tested during the last year and a half. Governmental bodies had to quickly adapt to the COVID-19 situation and make fundamental changes to their structure, policy making and communication mechanisms while implementing drastic measures to ensure the safety of their populations. The assessment of

these responses is an ongoing endeavor, and this report constitutes a first step towards the better understanding of the Governments' preparedness during the crisis. The COVINFORM project is determined to furtherly explore and evaluate the decisions made by Governmental stakeholders, especially regarding vulnerable groups, by undertaking empirical research in the following months, with the purpose of providing helpful and actionable suggestions.

Useful Material

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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**Using an intersectional
lens to understand the
unequal impact of the
COVID-19 pandemic**

Bi-Monthly Report: 05

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INTRODUCTION

Since its emergence in December 2019, COVID-19 has had far-reaching consequences for societies around the globe. The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic go far beyond physical health, impacting individuals' and communities' everyday lives and well-being, including in the domains of education, employment, family life, and mental health. However, the pandemic has not affected everybody's lives in the same way. Indeed, the crisis has unfolded across pre-existing social fault lines in societies, exposing and exacerbating inequalities (Kawachi, 2020). The pandemic is socially patterned not just in terms of COVID-19 morbidity and mortality rates, but also in terms of the impact of the implemented restrictions and emergency lockdown measures (Bambra et al., 2020). Intersectionality theory, a central tenet of the COVINFORM project's theoretical grounding, provides a useful foundation for exploring this socially patterned impact. An intersectional analytical approach dissects how lived experiences during the COVID-19 crisis are shaped by the interaction of different social factors such as gender, ethnicity, class, age, migration status, and religion.

This bi-monthly report draws upon insights from COVINFORM desk-based research assess COVID-19 public health impact and responses to across COVINFORM partner countries: Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Israel, Ireland, Italy, Germany, Greece, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom (England and Wales). The goal of this report is to outline the usefulness of an intersectional lens in considering how pre-existing structural inequalities influence COVID-19 morbidity and mortality rates, as well as in understanding how COVID-19 containment measures interact with existing structural inequalities across partner countries.

The report first provides a brief introduction to intersectionality theory, highlighting its relevance for analyses of the COVID-19 pandemic. It then considers how exposure to COVID-19, as well as risk of severe disease and mortality, are shaped by pre-existing societal structures that give rise to specific inequalities. Subsequently, it presents examples of how responses to the COVID-19 crisis, such as mobility restrictions, school closures, and restrictions on events and businesses, have been experienced differently depending on people's positions in society. Throughout this report, special emphasis is placed on how people's positions at the intersections of various axes of inequality result in specific outcomes at the individual level. The report concludes by presenting some recommendations on including an intersectional lens in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic and similar crises.

INTERSECTIONALITY THEORY AND ITS RELEVANCE IN THE COVID-19 CONTEXT

Intersectionality theory provides a critical framework for examining how the interconnections and interdependencies between social and political identities contribute to varying modes of discrimination and privilege (Atewologun, 2018). An intersectional analytical approach allows us to view how experiences of disadvantage are shaped by the interaction of different social factors such as gender, ethnicity, class, age, religion, and migration status. These social factors create “multilayered and routinized forms of domination that often converge” (Crenshaw, 1990, p. 1245). In other words, connected systems and structures of power create interdependent systemic bases of privilege and oppression (Hankivsky et al., 2014).

The concept of intersectionality emerged from the racialised experiences of minority ethnic women in the United States, notably through the work critical race theorist Kimberlé Williams Crenshaw, who sought to draw attention to how the treatment of African American women within US law needs to consider the dual lenses of gender and race discrimination (Crenshaw, 1989). As a theory with broad relevance, intersectionality theory provides a “lens through which you can see where power comes and collides, where it interlocks and intersects” (Crenshaw, 2017).

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, an intersectional lens facilitates a move away from thinking merely about clearly delineated groups or single risk factors. Instead, it encourages us to take into account the multitude of inequalities and disadvantages which determine how the impact of the pandemic is experienced by communities and individuals (Hankivsky, 2020). As a result of interacting social factors, people often belong to more than one social group. For example, an elderly immigrant woman living with disability may be disadvantaged in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic in several different ways. Using an intersectionality approach provides the mindset and language for examining for how members of heterogeneous groups of people may experience the COVID-19 pandemic differently depending on their gender, ethnicity, occupation, and other social characteristics.

EXISTING INEQUALITY STRUCTURES SHAPE THE DIFFERENTIAL SPREAD AND HEALTH IMPACT OF COVID-19

The risk of contracting COVID-19, as well as the risk of falling seriously ill or dying from COVID-19, is not equally distributed within and across societies. In exploring these differences, it is important to distinguish between the role of pre-existing health inequalities and the role of differential exposure to COVID-19.

Health status & structural health inequalities

Firstly, some people are at higher risk of becoming very ill or dying from COVID-19 as a result of their pre-existing health status (Bradley et al., 2020). Figure 1 shows how across countries, COVID-19 death rates are typically slightly higher among men. Death rates are also unequally distributed by age: using Italian data, figure 2 highlights how COVID-19 death rates differ significantly both by sex and age. Apart from the elderly, clinically vulnerable groups are often also considered to include adults with type 2 diabetes; adults with severe chronic cardiovascular, lung or kidney disease; and adults with decreased immunity and/or cancer (e.g. see VAZG, 2020). Some countries, such as Ireland, consider a relatively wide range of other people to be clinically vulnerable, too, e.g. including individuals with a severe mental illness and people with a learning disability (HSE, 2021).

COVID-19 deaths sex-disaggregated

Figure 1. Data source: the Sex, Gender and COVID-19 Project.

Italy: COVID-19 deaths by sex and age (rates per 100,000)

Figure 2. Data source: the Sex, Gender and COVID-19 Project.

Individuals' age and health status cannot be separated from other aspects of their identity and the circumstances in which they live. Indeed, it is important to acknowledge that being at higher risk from (severe) COVID-19 disease based on physical health status is intricately linked with structural health inequalities (Bambra et al., 2020). A range of non-medical factors influence

health outcomes, frequently grouped under the umbrella label 'social determinants of health'. Social, economic and environmental inequalities shape people's ability to prevent sickness, their risk of getting ill, as well as their access to treatment (Dahlgren & Whitehead, 1991), hereby influencing the distribution of health and illness in societies.

The social determinants of health are the conditions in which people are born, grow, live, work, and age. Differences in these conditions lead to health inequities.

In the case of COVID-19, existing inequalities in the distribution of chronic diseases – which pose important risk factors for severe COVID-19 infections – are of particular relevance. Across Europe, people in the lowest income group are much more likely to have a chronic illness than people with the highest incomes (Scholz, 2020). Although ethnic variations in chronic disease rates in Europe remain poorly understood (Bhopal, 2009), rates of chronic diseases have also been reported to be higher among ethnic minority groups in several European countries (Modesti et al., 2016). In line with this, data from countries like the USA and the UK has revealed that individuals belonging to migrant or ethnic minority groups face systematically high levels of severe COVID-19 illness and mortality (Sze et al., 2020). In the UK, COVID-19 death rates have been reported to be highest among Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic (BAME) persons (Otu et al., 2020).

An intersectional lens helps highlight that these types of differences in rates of severe COVID-19 illness and mortality are not ‘natural’: instead, they are the outcome of a complex array of power structures and societal processes that shape the social determinants of health. As such, intersectionality theory can help us understand how the unequal health impacts of COVID-19 are avoidable and unjust. A focus on intersectionality also accentuates how people who are disadvantaged in terms of their pre-existing health status may actually face an accumulation of different drivers of disadvantage, e.g. through a combination of having a low income, having a chronic illness, and experiencing discriminatory treatment in the healthcare system. All of these drivers may contribute to an individual’s oppression and discrimination in society, and each axis of oppression is likely to reinforce and interact with other axes.

Exposure to COVID-19

The differential spread of COVID-19 is also influenced by the risk of exposure to the virus faced by different groups in society. For instance, the extent to which people are able to adhere to physical distancing and protect themselves from viral transmission is heavily influenced by their employment and housing. Some individuals and groups of people are more exposed to contracting COVID-19 because of their job. Lower-paid workers, such as those working in cleaning, food or delivery services, are unable to work from home and have been required to travel to work even throughout lockdown periods, often by public transport (Bambra et al., 2020).

The risk of exposure to COVID-19 is affected by various factors, including employment, housing and transportation.

Indeed, many of the COVID-19 outbreaks in non-healthcare workplaces have been reported in industries deemed ‘essential’ where conditions do not allow for adequate physical distancing under the same productivity targets, such as meat processing plants (MPPs) and other food production and processing facilities. Outbreaks in MPPs have been reported in many COVINFORM partner countries, including Germany, Ireland, the UK, Spain, Belgium, Italy, Austria and Sweden (EFFAT, 2020). Such COVID-19 outbreaks are thought not only to result from working conditions in the MPPs, such as the close proximity of workers, but also from workers’ shared transportation and housing, which facilitate transmission of the virus (Dyal et al., 2020). Health workers also face a higher risk of contracting COVID-19 compared to the general population (Gómez-Ochoa et al., 2021). Female health care workers, and black women in particular, face higher rates of COVID-19 infections than their male counterparts (Lotta et al., 2021). Apart from working conditions, housing is an important factor to consider in

COVID-19 transmission as well. People living in poverty typically have poorer quality and smaller housing (or are homeless), which means they are more exposed to the virus and are likely to struggle more with stay-at-home orders. Evidence from the UK revealed that living in crowded housing is associated with an 11% increase in age-adjusted COVID-19 mortality rates (Daras et al., 2021).

The intersectionality framework helps shed light on how it is typically the multiply disadvantaged that are at highest risk of exposure to COVID-19. Those who are disadvantaged in various ways – e.g. those with lower-paid jobs, without car access and living in cramped housing – are most exposed. Going beyond a focus on a single socio-economic factor such as ‘low-income’, the framework demonstrates how the simultaneous and interconnected influence of issues like the gendered division of labour (e.g. the overrepresentation of women in lower-paid care jobs) and the overrepresentation of ethnic minority groups among frontline ‘essential workers’ (Sze et al., 2020) contribute to the unequal health impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

COVID-19 CONTAINMENT MEASURES INTERACT WITH EXISTING SYSTEMS OF INEQUALITY

Across COVINFORM partner countries, the measures enacted to curb the spread of COVID-19 have been associated with significant disruption and socio-economic consequences. Examples of such measures include travel restrictions, quarantine measures, shop and restaurant closures or restrictions, school closures or distant learning, and work-from-home orders. A consideration of the impact of COVID-19 responses on various domains of everyday life highlights how some individuals have disproportionately faced far-reaching negative consequences. We provide a brief, non-comprehensive analysis of such intersectional disadvantage in the contexts of work and care responsibilities, impacts faced by children, digitalisation, and experiences of discrimination and policing.

Work and care responsibilities

Firstly, the COVID-19 containment measures have had far-ranging consequences for people's working realities and caring responsibilities. Key drivers of change in this domain have been work-from-home recommendations, closure of childcare facilities, and remote learning for children and young people. According to an EU survey, the negative impact of COVID-19 on work-life balance has been felt most strongly by women, particularly those with young children (Ahrendt et al., 2020). In

Belgium, a research study on the impact of lockdown measures on the division of responsibilities within Belgian households during the first lockdown in spring 2020 revealed that traditional role divisions had been reinforced (Glorieux & Van Tienoven, 2020). Women have been more likely to have been forced to sacrifice paid work in order to compensate for the loss of childcare during lockdowns (Allmendinger, 2020). Data from Switzerland indicates that these gendered role divisions led to more stress and mental health complaints for women compared to men during the COVID-19 crisis (Kuhn et al., 2021). An intersectional lens allows us to note that some women have fewer resources to allow them to cope with increased care burdens (e.g. more responsibilities, lower savings, less support), with racialized women, single parents, and women with disabilities among the groups who are disproportionately hit (Hankivsky & Kapilashrami, 2020).

As a result of the distinctly gendered nature of existing professional and care structures in society (UNFPA, 2020), the economic impact of the COVID-19 crisis has also played out differently along intersections of profession and gender. For example, the pandemic has led to a loss of jobs in many women-dominated professions, such as hairdressers, flight attendants, and workers in restaurants and shops (Buikema, 2020). The economic impact of the pandemic has been particularly significant for women working in the informal sector, compared to women in formal sector work (Birchall, 2021). Disadvantage at the intersection of profession and gender is frequently combined with having a migrant background and/or belonging to an ethnic or racial minority in society, as some ethnic/racial minority groups and/or migrant groups are overrepresented in specific professions. For example, women of colour and women with fewer years of education are overrepresented in the most precarious 'frontline' healthcare and homecare jobs (e.g. Belgium: Furia, 2020; Austria: Wölfl, 2020).

Children and education

Lockdown measures and home schooling have posed challenges to all children and their families, but some experience a greater accumulation of various layers of disadvantage.

Across partner countries, single parents or large families were considered to experience disproportionate impacts, particularly those families who also face poverty and social exclusion (e.g. see FPS Social Security, 2020; Prainsack et al., 2020). As schools have closed for prolonged periods in many partner countries, existing educational inequalities are likely to be exacerbated (Markowitz, 2021). Online learning environments usually require a computer for each learner, a reliable internet connection and a suitable calm place to study, which not all families can offer (UNIA, 2020). In Romania, for instance, a study conducted in March-June 2020 revealed that only 3% of Roma children participated in online lessons (Hackl, 2020). Similarly, an Irish research review by Darmody et al. (2020) suggests that students from migrant backgrounds, including Irish Traveller students, were likely to be more heavily impacted by the impact of COVID-19 school closures than children from Irish backgrounds. This is related to families' resources and skills to assist their child's learning at home, families' time availability (e.g. essential workers are typically able to spend less time on home-schooling), as well as to school closures' impact on students' access to additional support (e.g. literacy support and special needs support) (Darmody et al., 2020).

Digitalisation

The COVID-19 crisis has accelerated the ongoing digitalisation of society, as many services and vital systems have been forced to use virtual platforms and solutions (Miladinovic, 2020). However, not everyone has been able to take advantage of such technologies, which means the digitalisation sparked by COVID-19 has effectively cut some people off from social contacts, public services, cultural experiences, and educational opportunities (Coene et al., 2020). For example, there seems to be an emerging ‘digital gap’ for learning as a result of the increased reliance on remote learning and home schooling for children. As such, intersectional disadvantage related to digitalisation may be experienced particularly by children who do not have the appropriate resources/facilities for home-schooling (e.g., laptops, separate rooms, reliable internet connection), and whose parents do not speak the language of instruction or are not familiar with the curriculum (e.g. Italy: Marchetti & Guiducci, 2020; Belgium: UNIA, 2020). For many older people, isolation and loneliness has been worsened by their lack of digital skills or access to digital technologies. As such, disadvantage linked to digital gaps may lie at the intersection of age, socioeconomic status, low literacy, disability, and mental illness (Coene et al., 2020).

Discrimination & policing

For some groups of people, the COVID-19 has also been associated with an increase in discriminatory experiences. In Belgium, for instance, many people with an Asian appearance or physical characteristics faced racist remarks and aggression at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic (Slaats, 2020; Struys, 2020). In Austria, an increased occurrence of discrimination based on religious grounds was also noted (SOS Mitmensch, 2021). Many reports of discrimination also relate to the discriminatory enforcement of lockdown rules, e.g. in the context of stop and search and identity checks as police enforced lockdown measures. In the UK, London police registered a 22% increase in stop and searches between March-April 2020, and the proportion of black people searched increased by nearly a third (Amnesty International, 2020). As many of the government measures have been vaguely defined, considerable room for interpretation of the rules remains, which seems to facilitate ethnic profiling in their enforcement (Clementi, 2020; Van Thienen, 2020). To sum up, experiences of discrimination and unfair policing in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic are frequently positioned at the intersection of race/ethnicity, gender, class and religion.

PROMISING PRACTICES FOR INCLUDING AN INTERSECTIONAL LENS

Our analysis has shown how pre-existing structural inequalities influence COVID-19 infection and mortality rates, as well how COVID-19 containment measures interact with existing systems of inequality. The intersectionality framework has helped highlight how some individuals are simultaneously impacted by various axes of oppression, placing them in a particularly vulnerable position in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. Intersecting factors which seem to be of particular relevance in analyses of the COVID-19 crisis are gender, age, socio-economic status, disability, family composition, race/ethnicity, and migrant background.

Although some COVID-19 policy responses and measures have acknowledged that some groups of people face multiple, simultaneous drivers of disadvantage and marginalization, policy initiatives rarely explicitly take an intersectional approach. Indeed, policy responses typically assume a subject who only faces one type of social difficulty or barrier (Crenshaw, 1989), which arguably leads to a fragmentation of the responses. In this section, we provide some recommendations on promising practices for including an intersectional lens in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic and similar crises.

Firstly, intersectional approaches require the collection of diverse data that is aggregated by various social characteristics. Data disaggregated by gender, ethnic identity, occupation, disability, age, and migration or refugee status would shed more light on which groups experience disproportionate impacts (Berkhout & Richardson, 2020; Hankivsky, 2020). Data should also be collected from multiple sources, including by practitioners, governments, and civil society. Multiple methodologies should be used, including qualitative and mixed-methods approaches which are well-suited to capturing the lived experiences of diverse groups of people (Ryan & El Ayadi, 2020). Data should be contextualized by considering how the effects of the crisis/pandemic are situated in socioeconomic and political contexts, and are linked to societal and cultural values and norms (Hankivsky & Kapilashrami, 2020).

Intersectional responses are inevitably cross-sectoral. Addressing interlocking outcomes of unequal power systems requires coordination of policies across sectors like education, housing, social protection, employment and legal services (Hankivsky & Kapilashrami, 2020).

Although the COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated that welfare state policies can play an important role in cushioning the unequal impact of crises (e.g. through specific

support or compensation measures), the crisis also revealed how policies in different sectors often remain siloed. Placing intersectional perspectives at the heart of social welfare states would serve the dual aim of addressing social inequalities at the root and prioritising assistance for those facing intersectional disadvantage.

Furthermore, intersectional responses should include efforts to support and promote leaders from a range of communities and local organizations. Such strategies can facilitate the involvement of disadvantaged communities to be part of the development and implementation of solutions, instead of merely prescribing them (Berkhout & Richardson, 2020). Moving beyond a deficit model, policy and decision-makers should use resilience and asset-based approaches, and prioritize participatory engagement mechanisms among affected communities. This also requires a commitment to leadership diversity, including substantive participation of women, people living with disability, and people from minority religious and ethnic backgrounds (Hankivsky & Kapilashrami, 2020). Only by fostering community participation can interventions be tailored and adapted to address the unique intersecting inequalities faced by individuals in various local contexts.

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The COVINFORM project

Acronym	COVINFORM
Title	Coronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFORMATION dynamics Research and Modelling
Coordinator	SYNYO GmbH
Reference	101016247
Type	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Programme	HORIZON 2020
Topic	SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2C Behavioural, social and economic impacts of the outbreak response
Start	01 November 2020
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Contact

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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**The impact of
COVID-19 pandemic on
healthcare workers.**

Bi-Monthly Report: 06

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INTRODUCTION

In Italy, 144,812 cases of COVID-19 have been recorded in **healthcare workers (HCWs)**, out of which 1,444 were reported in October 2022. The World Health Organization (WHO) suggested that worldwide 115,000 HCWs died from COVID-19 between January 2020 and May 2021. The unpreparedness of health systems worldwide has left HCWs exposed to a higher risk of contagion than the general population, enclosing them into a high vulnerability group. Aim of this bi-monthly report is to summarize the impact of COVID-19 on HCWs.

ARE HCWS AT INCREASED RISK?

Any human activity involves potential risks, especially during a worldwide pandemic; however, some activities are simultaneously highly exposed and essential for the common good. HCWs are seven times more likely to catch severe COVID-19 infections than others in "non-essential" jobs (Mutambudzi et al., 2020). HCWs' job is to safeguard and improve the health of their communities (WHO, 2006), and they were called to make important sacrifices in the fight against COVID-19. HCWs had to face isolation from their families and society while struggling to save lives. The increased responsibilities and workload have imposed a significant mental and physical burden on HCWs. The unpreparedness of health systems worldwide has left HCWs exposed to a higher risk of contagion than the general population, enclosing them into a high vulnerability group (Smith, 2020). The current literature (Mhago et al., 2020) highlighted two types of risk conditions for HCWs: lack of personal protective equipment (PPE) and work overload. The

shortage of PPE affected almost all health systems worldwide during the first wave of the pandemic, but it is still an important issue in developing countries. Without PPE, drugs, and vaccines, HCWs have been exposed to higher infection rates than the general population due to close contact with infected patients (Nguyen et al., 2020). On the other hand, factors such as work overload and the absence of universally recognized protocols or guidelines caused by the pandemic's unpredictable nature have heavily impacted HCWs' psychological health (Mhago et al., 2020). A recent umbrella review (Fan et al., 2021) highlighted that prevention of HCWs' health risks should be a priority for both policymakers and public health authorities, who should develop risk mitigation strategies that can be translated into concrete interventions.

WHAT IS THE PSYCHOSOCIAL IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON HCWS?

Lots of studies have been conducted to analyse the impact of COVID-19 on people's psychological health and daily life. A recent meta-analysis (De Souza et al., 2021) has found that the COVID-19 pandemic has increased the prevalence of mental health problems from 20 to 36%; however, HCWs presented a higher prevalence of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) than the general population. HCWs showed a higher prevalence of intensified sleep disorders, stress levels and burnout syndrome, defined as psychophysiological stress conditions (De Souza et al., 2021). In the literature, the increased rates of anxiety and depression among HCWs have been the object of research (Fernandez et al., 2021; Abraham et al., 2021; Lenzo et al., 2021). These estimates are considered to be even higher since the data can be conditioned by the cultural taboo of 'not complaining' or the fear of being labelled as unstable. Inevitably, high rates of anxiety and

depression among HCWs were found in settings with higher rates of COVID-19 infection and mortality (Fernandez et al., 2021). Fernandez et al. (2021) suggested that these increases can be explained by the higher workload related to the pandemic peaks. The impact on HCWs' daily lives and sleep quality has significantly increased (De Souza et al., 2021). Insomnia disorders were common in many HCWs during the peaks of the pandemic (Mccall et al., 2021) and can impact their provision of care. To mitigate this impact, institutions and stakeholders should regularly screen HCWs for levels of insomnia and psychological disorders (Sahebi et al., 2021). The adoption of appropriate supportive measures and timely interventions can reduce the incidence of more severe psychological disorders that can impact long-term HCWs work efficiency (Sahebi et al., 2021). Figure 1 summarize the most common outcomes used to measure the impact of COVID-19 on HCWs.

Figure 1 - Most common COVID-19 impact outcomes on HCWs

WHAT CAN WE LEARN FROM HCWS' EXPERIENCES?

The issues linked to the pandemic risks for HCWs' mental and physical health have received enormous attention since the early waves. There have been numerous attempts of intervention to support HCWs' mental health and mitigate the long-term pandemic effects, but there is still a lack of consensus on which measures are the most helpful in this regard. HCWs' opinions and experiences on what type of support is the most effective for them are to consider in order to create support interventions that are appropriate, timely and in line with their needs (Billings et al., 2021). A recent meta-synthesis (Billings et al., 2021) on the experiences of frontline HCWs during the COVID-19 pandemic highlighted that one of the most critical aspects was access to help, which was often limited by HCWs' isolation and fear that their condition may not be fully understood by their colleagues of the psychological support service. This issue undermined HCWs' use of social support desks (Billings et al., 2021) and may have negative long-term consequences.

On the contrary, peer-support groups seem to have been highly appreciated by the HCWs (Billings et al., 2021). HCWs desired to share their burdens with someone they thought could understand them, having lived the same experience. Another systematic qualitative review (Koontalay et al., 2021) showed that HCWs felt inadequately prepared to face the pandemic. The onset of new emotional challenges and the lack of PPE and information were triggers that emotionally upset the HCWs, leading to burnout syndrome (Koontalay et al., 2021). Involving qualitative research in our analysis allows us to obtain a deeper understanding of the phenomenon, and policies and stakeholders should account for HCWs' narrations in their decision-making processes.

WHAT PROGRAMS HAVE BEEN DESIGNED TO MITIGATE COVID-19 EFFECTS ON HCWS?

Supporting the mental health of health care workers is one of the major challenges for the public health response during the COVID-19 pandemic. A recent systematic review (Buselli et al., 2021) showed that many supportive care programs were developed in various hospitals through a multidisciplinary approach. Supportive care involves the provision of emotional support through counselling or motivational interventions. Many of the supportive care interventions involved strategies such as team training, peers and institutional support. Buselli et al. (2021) stated that the common goal of all the supportive care programs was to manage the psychosocial impact of COVID-19 on HCWs and prevent long-term mental health problems. Many of these interventions are still ongoing; however, critical issues were related to the heterogeneity of protocols, the absence of rigorous procedures, and primary objective outcomes (Buselli et al., 2021). Even if the impact of COVID-19 on HCWs' mental health is well-known, it seems we still lack policies and a homogeneous

approach to deal with mental health problems. Drissi et al. (2021) systematic review showed that the majority of the mental health programs delivered by institutions to support HCWs were delivered digitally. Technology offers several solutions in managing psychological problems, and in the past years, we have faced an increase in the delivery of e-health interventions. Even is very heterogeneous in their core elements, the e-health interventions seemed to be effective in reducing stress and burnout among HCWs (Drissi et al., 2021). Drissi et al. (2021) suggested that the e-health interventions are well suited to meet the COVID-19 pandemic restriction measured and HCWs' support needs. Further research should be conducted to test the cost-benefit of digital psychological interventions compared to standard supportive care programs to inform policies. The main features of the programs designed to mitigate COVID-19 effects on HCWs are summarized in Figure 2.

Psycho-motivational support

- Motivational interventions
- Emotional support
- Counselling

Supportive care interventions

- Institutional support
- Team training
- Peers

E-Health

- Use of Information & Communication Technologies (ICT)
- Meet pandemic restrictions and HCWs needs

Digital psychological intervention

Rigorous procedure of support

Homogeneous policies

Figure 2 - Programs to mitigate COVID-19 impact on HCWs

A NEW CHALLENGE: HCWS AND VACCINE HESITANCY.

Given their vulnerability, HCWs were among the first to receive COVID-19 vaccines; however, a recent meta-analysis on vaccine hesitancy (Luo et al., 2021) suggested that only 51% of them were in favour of receiving the vaccine. This alarming data is confirmed by a substantial number of HCWs who remain hesitant after one year into the pandemic (Toth-Manikowski et al., 2021). While in December 2020 the hesitancy was likely due to the HCWs' worries about the efficacy and safety of the vaccines (Luo et al., 2021), nowadays, the reasons underneath HCWs' hesitancy are not clear. HCWs are a heterogeneous group, but they all have advanced knowledge and health literacy compared to the general population. Although there may be a general understanding that vaccines are safe and effective, not all HCWs have the same level of understanding about how vaccines work. The rates of vaccines hesitancy among HCWs vary by country, vaccine, and type of health professional. For example, a cross-sectional survey sent to French HCWs (Gagneux-Brunon et al., 2021) displayed

that, on average, pharmacists and physicians are less hesitant than nurses. Biswas et al. (2021) implied that the prevalence of vaccine hesitancy worldwide among HCWs ranged from 4.3 to 72%, with a weighted average of 22.51%. Factors such as older age, being male and holding a doctoral degree were associated with a reduction in vaccine hesitancy among HCWs (Biswas et al., 2021). Italy has been the first country to introduce mandatory vaccination for HCWs, which has contributed to a lower infection rate in the past months. Nowadays, no comprehensive statistical analysis exists on the vaccine hesitancy among HCWs. HCWs play a key role in pandemic management and represent a model of behaviours for the general population, and the issue of HCWs' vaccine hesitancy should be taken seriously. Communication and training strategies should be implemented to increase vaccination uptake (Biswas et al., 2021). Other strategies to increase vaccine confidence may rely on participatory approaches, such as motivational interventions, but further studies are needed.

HOW CAN WE MEASURE COVID-19 IMPACT ON HCWS?

Monitoring and measuring the impact of COVID-19 on HCWs has been a challenge since the beginning of the pandemic. COVID-19 has impacted psychological and social dimensions, which are subjective and difficult to measure. Many scales have been designed and validated to measure the psychological impact of COVID-19 on HCWs. Chung et al. (2020) developed the Stress and Anxiety to Viral Epidemics-9 (SAVE-9) scale for assessing work-related stress and anxiety in HCWs in response to COVID-19. The SAVE-9 has shown good internal consistency and construct validity (Chung et al., 2020; Tavormina et al., 2020). The Tokyo Metropolitan Distress Scale for Pandemic (Shiwaku et al., 2021) was developed to measure the psychological impact of COVID-19

on HCWS, and it has adequate construct validity and convergent validity. Alternatively, reliable scales such as the Posttraumatic Stress Disorder Checklist for DSM-5 (Cheng et al., 2020), the Impact of Event Scale Revised (Marcomini et al., 2021) and the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales-21 (Lenzo et al., 2021) were used. A scoping review of the existing scale measuring the impact of COVID-19 (Chandu et al., 2020) highlights that the majority of the scales focus on psychiatric symptoms rather than psychosocial. Moreover, many scales were not designed ad hoc for HCWs and do not assess a comprehensive measure to document all the mental health problems posed by the COVID-19 pandemic (Chandu et al., 2020).

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COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation
dynamics Research and Modelling

**Viruses of the mind.
Coping and joking
about COVID-19**

Bi-Monthly Report: 07

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'GOING VIRAL': HUMOUR AS A COPING MECHANISM

This report presents outcomes of an explorative analysis of memes conducted in the context of the COVIFORM project. Our aim was to gain an understanding of how humour was used to cope with the events of the pandemic and communicate with others, to share specific narratives, and to comment on experiences during the pandemic.

Humour is a powerful coping mechanism. During this global health crisis with drastic effects, humour can lower the degree of negative emotions such as stress and hopelessness which often surround the pandemic (Olah & Ford 2021). Internet memes are commonly used to comment on current issues; they “facilitate discursive exchanges about events within society and criticism of these events” (Pauliks 2020, 47). As the pandemic began to dominate the public discourse, researchers could observe the production and sharing of large amounts of COVID-19-related memes (Strick 2021). Analysing these timely COVID-19 memes is an opportunity to gain preliminary insights into the relationship of meme creation and sharing and an global event such as the current pandemic.

What are memes?

Internet memes can be defined as “(a) a group of digital items sharing common characteristics of content, form, and/or stance, which (b) were created with awareness of each other, and (c) were circulated, imitated and/or transformed via the Internet by many users” (Shifman 2014, 41). The term "meme" is commonly used to describe the propagation of jokes, rumours, videos and the like via the internet, thus being closely connected to Dawkins' initial idea of describing small units of culture spreading from person to person by copying or imitation (ibid.). Memes allow different audiences to make sense of the same media artefact; they bring together folk practices and contemporary media (Miltner 2018).

Humour allows us to address sensitive topics in creating a critical distance from the topic; it can also be used to express criticism (Pauliks 2020) and to cope with stressful situations. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused several domains of stress (Olah & Ford 2021; Schimmenti et al. 2020), namely

- bodily (such as physical health concerns);
- interpersonal (such as isolation, concerns for family members);
- cognitive (processing frightening information);
- behavioural;
- economic; and
- political.

METHODOLOGY

For our analysis, we collected and exploratively analysed memes, focussing on ten countries of research. While we defined a general search strategy, the selection of keywords and channels varied per country to address the country-specific differences in the way memes are generated and shared. For all countries, the search was conducted in a combination of search via keywords and identification of relevant channels such as Reddit, Imgur, 9gag, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter etc. This resulted in a sample of 668 memes collected between the beginning of 2020 and autumn 2021 within the ten countries of analysis.

Table 1. Overview memes collected per country

Austria	Belgium	Germany	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Romania	Spain	Sweden	UK	Total
275	36	38	11	62	76	10	70	35	55	668

Following the logic of Panofsky's (1962) iconographic-iconological method, the images were coded inductively in line with the explorative approach. Categories were created through identifying themes within the data set.

Due to the diversity of the sample, as well as the differences in numbers of memes collected per country, we conducted a high-level analysis that does not claim representability. The type of images included may not only be caused by country-specific characteristics but also by the search strategies applied. As such, while providing some insights in how humour was used to cope with the pandemic situation, this analysis provides an exploration of the topic.

'PEOPLE IN THE UK RIGHT NOW' – JOKING AND COPING DURING A PANDEMIC

Memes were used across all countries under research to joke about and cope with the consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic. In this report we focus on three categories or overarching themes we identified throughout the memes across all countries under research:

- joking about the current situation to cope with everyday life in the pandemic,
- a commentary on the measures, and
- criticism of the behaviour of other members in society.

COPING WITH EVERYDAY LIFE DURING THE PANDEMIC

Memes across the ten countries under research comment on measures as a **coping mechanism, discussing struggles of the everyday life with the pandemic**. Curfews, home office, home schooling and other lockdown-related restrictions were a new and often stressful situation for many persons. This meant that people had to find ways to cope with the situation. One example is provided in **Figure 1**: the meme shows a man wearing a hoodie, sunglasses, and headphones while standing in his bathtub, pretending to be on the public transport he uses for his daily commute. The accompanying text states “#StayAtHome. However, keep your daily routine”. This meme is a comment on how residents are advised to follow the lockdown order but also keep up their daily routines.

Another example of coping with the **disruption of ‘normal life’** is provided in **Figure 2**. The text says “When your hairdresser is closed, but the dog groomer who is working from home is still available”. This is accompanied with a picture of a young man with a peculiar, poodle-like hairstyle. The meme refers to a time in Belgium during which hairdressers and other services were closed. In a joking way, it provides ideas for alternative ways to get a haircut. A similar example is shown **Figure 3**: a man with a smug smile, tipping his finger to his head, is accompanied by a text that reads “Wearing double mask at the gym is not bothering if you are not going to the gym”. Posted in May 2021, when first restrictions were lifted, this image reacts to

Figure 1. Everyday life during the pandemic | Portugal

Figure 2. Everyday life during the pandemic | Belgium

the Greek government's recommendation to wear double masks at the gym. Such memes address the limitations of everyday life due to restrictions, and the challenges experienced during the pandemic due to these measures.

Other memes in this category may be described as **'self-mockery', addressing particular stereotypes or national peculiarities**. One example is the stereotype that Swedish people are shy, avoid crowds and like to keep to themselves which comes in handy during the pandemic as physical distancing is effective in stopping the spread of COVID- 19. The meme shown in **Figure 4** is a good example of this: it displays two identical images depicting three persons waiting for a bus, before and after the COVID-19 crisis. The joke refers to the distance Swedish people keep from each other, even prior to the pandemic.

In a similar way, there are memes that **comment on the everyday behaviour during the pandemic, often in a mild-mannered form of mockery**. One example is the meme displayed in **Figure 5**, which shows a picture of the actor Daniel Craig in the film 'James Bond'. The British secret agent is pointing a disinfectant spray, in place of a gun. Additionally, the actor is seen wearing personal protective equipment, a mask, as encouraged in public health recommendations to prevent the spread of coronavirus. The image was posted in early winter 2020, during the second wave of the pandemic. At this time, public health campaigns strongly emphasised adherence to hygiene measures. At this time in pandemic when vaccines were not yet available, and with increased risks of transmission during the winter months, behavioural strategies were the only means of protection that people could exercise.

Figure 3. Everyday life during the pandemic | Greece

Figure 4. Everyday life during the pandemic | Sweden

Figure 5. Everyday life during the pandemic | UK

MOCKING COVID-19 MEASURES

Besides addressing the challenges of everyday life during the pandemic, memes commented or **criticised measures implemented to fight the pandemic**. This tackles measures that are seen as too ‘soft’ to actually stop the spread of the virus, as well as when measures that were perceived as exaggerated and restrictive. Furthermore, there are memes addressing measures seen as unreasonable or confusing.

An example of the first aspect, **measures seen as too ‘soft’**, is provided in **Figure 6**: it shows a door locked only with a cheese doodle with the text “states are trying to stop the spread of the virus by making restaurants close a 10 pm”. Similar memes were identified in other countries; it may be a commentary on times of uncertainty, where the population felt particularly frightened by the pandemic, yet measures were not that strict.

Contrary to that are **memes commenting on measures that are experienced as too restricting**, as exemplified in **Figure 7**. The picture shows Italy's former Premier Giuseppe Conte making a speech to the citizens. The text captions state “I won't even let the surprise out of the Easter egg”. Published in April 2020, this meme refers to the restrictions implemented in Italy during the Easter holidays, experienced as restricting by some.

states trying to stop the spread of the coronavirus by making restaurants close at 10pm

Figure 6. Commentary on measures | Sweden

Figure 7. Commentary on measures | Italy

Finally, memes comment on the **constantly changing nature of the pandemic**, which means that governments often had to adapt measures, which – at times – was seen as confusing. One example from Austria is provided in **Figure 8**: in three screenshots of a scene in The Lord of the Rings. The Fellowship of the Ring, the text captions state Pippin saying: “Do you already know the new corona rules for new years?” to which Aragon says: “They are known already for a week.” Pippin replies: “These are the old new rules. I mean the new new rules.” This kind of commentary on the ever-changing nature of the measures, as well as the confusion when measures were modified slightly so differences were not entirely clear, could be found across the countries under analysis.

Figure 8. Commentary on measures | Austria

COMMENTARY ON BEHAVIOUR

Across all countries, we could find **memes commenting on the behaviour of other members of society during the pandemic**. This includes non-compliance with measures (such as wearing masks), as well as behaviour such as panic buying and hoarding of goods (particularly toilet paper; cf. Pauliks 2020), and the anti-vax movement. While there are differences (e.g., due to different measures), we could observe this category across all ten countries under research.

Non-compliance with measures such as wearing masks, keeping distance, staying at home, or avoiding gatherings of people is an issue that was commented across the countries under research. For example, the refusal of staying at home during lockdowns is exemplified in **Figure 9**: using screenshots of the TV sitcom ‘Friends’, Phoebe says ‘stay at home’, while Joey repeats ‘go to the coast’. This refers to the first lockdown in March 2020, when many Belgians went to the coast or other outdoor/nature areas, despite stay-at-home orders, and these places often became very crowded. This is one of many examples; across countries, memes commented on non-compliance, excuses, and ‘loopholes’ found by the population.

Another sub-category are memes **addressing hoarding** (e.g., of toilet paper), which were mainly shared at the beginning of the pandemic. An example is **Figure 10**: the picture shows as child eating breakfast. Instead of cereal, he is eating toilet paper. In the two speech bubbles above the picture, the boy asks, “Mom, when does this corona-story end?”, to which she answers, “Shut

Figure 9. Commentary on behaviour | Belgium

Figure 10. Commentary on behaviour | Sweden

up and eat your toilet paper”. Not only in Sweden, but across the globe, memes commenting on hoarding were shared in March 2020. These memes were referenced in later waves, particularly when lockdowns were introduced again.

The third sub-category of this commentary of behaviour is directed at the **anti-vaccination movement**. The example provided in **Figure 11** shows a frame of *Modern Educayshun* (2015), a short YouTube comedy by Neel Kolhatkar that explores and criticizes an alleged hypersensitive culture followed by social media and political correctness. The frame shows a young woman, the subtitles underneath her say “Stop violating me with your different opinion”. The meme comments the frame by saying “Me *uses facts and logic to prove that vaccines are good for you*. Anti-vaxxers:” The Twitter user introduces the meme by saying that after seeing an antivaxxer protest in Birmingham, the city can be now compared to an American one, joking about the scepticisms around vaccines in the US that is translated in a low vaccination rate.

This is one of several examples; across the countries under research, the often-emotional debate around the vaccines is taken up in memes reflecting on the subject.

Figure 11. Commentary on behaviour | UK

CONCLUSIONS

Whether addressing the current, uncertain situation, the behaviour of others, or the unfamiliar and restricting measures, internet memes are used to comment on experiences; they act as a “funhouse mirror for culture and society, reflecting and refracting the anxieties and preoccupations of a variety of social groups across a series of national contexts” (Miltner 2018, 413). Through their multimodal format, using both image and text, and through their popularity, memes can have an important role in establishing and maintaining discourse, driven by a need to express and reconstrue viewpoints (Dancygier & Vandelanotte 2017).

What we can observe in the memes we analysed is that they are used to share experiences in this unique situation. This may create a sense of togetherness – we can observe similarities across national borders – and it is a way to cope with the unfamiliarity and uncertainty of the situation. As a “viewpoint-driven multimodal construction” (Dancygier & Vandelanotte 2017, 568), memes are also used in the form of social commentary, as a way to express criticism. Humour in memes enables them to this political critique and commentary; and it is a way of mobilising and dissemination (Miltner 2018).

This report has presented a snapshot of the commentary on the pandemic situation through memes. Memes do not follow national borders and do not exist in isolation; they are re-used and follow the rules of online discourse communities (Dancygier & Vandelanotte 2017) using intertextual references. As such, this report does not give a comprehensive overview of the way experiences throughout the pandemic have been discussed in this format; rather, this was an exploration of themes and topics to gain some understanding in the use of humour to cope with – and joke about – the pandemic.

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The COVINFORM project

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Title	COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation dynamics Research and Modelling
Coordinator	SYNYO GmbH
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Type	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
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Topic	SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2C Behavioural, social and economic impacts of the outbreak response
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Duration	36 months

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2.8 Bi-monthly report 8: After two years of pandemic: COVINFORM partners talk about the experiences, challenges and lessons learned

After two years of pandemic | COVINFORM Bi-monthly report #8, March 2022.

COVINFORM partners talk about the experiences, challenges and lessons learned. Monika Stickler from the Austrian Red Cross and Paloma Miravet from the Spanish Samur talk about their work, the institution they work for, and their experience during the pandemic, focusing on the challenges and consequences of the pandemic and also on the lessons learned during the past two years.

The full interview is available [here](#)

3 Conclusions

The bi-monthly reports published so far have had the dual objective of addressing relevant issues related to the COVID-19 pandemic, such as vaccination campaigns and healthcare workers' conditions, and also presenting some of the first results of the project. Most of the bi-monthly reports were published in brochure format, with an appealing, schematic style and language that would capture the attention of the general public. The eighth report opened a season of experimenting with new formats to alternate with the classic brochure, such as video interviews. Certainly, the future results of the various activities of the project will constitute useful material for the reports, and the formats will be adapted to the topics that will be subjects of the reports. Since part of the target of the bi-monthly reports is constituted by the stakeholders, we will try, as already done, especially with the last bi-monthly report, to involve directly the practitioners, in order to make these reports even more effective in their purpose.

In order to do so, during the WP leaders meeting held in Rome in November 2021, we had brainstorming sessions about formats of bi-monthly reports. Here is a short summary of the discussion points that came up during the meeting. For the format the following one were proposed:

- Webinars (also exploiting synergies with sister projects)
- Record webinar and make short videos, generate quotes from experts – easily consumable
- Infographic, comics, creative materials – avoiding information fatigue
- Podcast (ca. 20 minutes), expert interviews, particularly practitioner partners
- Differences in communication / information campaigns
- Create test/game “do you know the measures?” – like a quiz but with scientific results, informative
- Fun facts e.g. what song to sing while washing the hands for 30 seconds

As for the target group the following one were suggested:

- Tailor to different target groups
- Target vulnerable groups with easy messages (e.g., pregnant women or HCWs)

We have planned to organise another brainstorming session during the Consortium meeting (Lisbon, May 2022). We have organised regular bi-monthly calls (together to WP9) to discuss about the content of bi-monthly report.

The bi-monthly reports allow to contribute in a practical way to the knowledge and development of expertise and best practices for all those (workers, volunteers, scientists, policymakers, etc.) involved in activities related to the project topics and in the crisis management. Thanks to the smart and fast fruition of the project topics and main results, bi-monthly reports represent relevant instruments for the dissemination and for the transition from the project to the reality and actions. The goal for the coming months is to continue to fulfil this purpose, continuing to follow the path already marked out and, at the same time, trying to invest in new topics and new formats.